

6 April 2009

Renée Crain
Arctic Research Support and Logistics
Office of Polar Programs – Division of Arctic Sciences
National Science Foundation
4201 Wilson Boulevard
Arlington, VA 22230

Dear Ms. Crain:

Attached is a *revised* 2nd Annual Program Plan and Annual Report of the Arctic Research Consortium of the U.S. (ARCUS) Cooperative Agreement ARC-0618885, between NSF and ARCUS. The report describes accomplishments for the period 1 April 2008 through 31 December 2008 and projected activities for 1 January 2009 through 31 December 2009, the second year of this agreement, with all necessary budget information and justification, and relevant appendices.

Included, as specified in the Cooperative Agreement, are:

1. A narrative summary of accomplishments, future plans, and discussion of major change in direction or pace, by individual task, including a timeline of activities and related appendices;
2. A one-page budget summary showing costs by five major tasks: Arctic Community Science Planning, NSF Arctic Sciences Section coordination, Arctic Science Education, Information and Outreach, and Core Support (Attachment A);
3. A five-page, multi-column table, by individual activity, showing the currently approved five-year budget, the actual costs for Year 1, the remaining funds or shortfall, and the proposed budget for 1 January 2009 – 31 December 2009 (Attachment B);
4. A one-page, multi-column table summarizing the entire CA by Form 1030 categories, showing the currently approved five-year budget, the actual costs for Year 1, the remaining funds or shortfall, and the proposed budget for 1 January 2009 – 31 December 2009 (Attachment C); and
5. The proposed budget and the request for **\$1,933,293** for the period of 1 January 2009 – 31 December 2009 on NSF Form 1030 (Attachment D).

This revised plan and budget differs from the past submission (submitted 3/27/09) with a budget reduction of the “Arctic Science Education” task from \$43,162 to \$27,079, as per your request; the activities cut includes travel for ARCUS staff and other participants for arctic science education activities, and a small reduction in the education publication budget.

The ARCUS Board of Directors and staff are very pleased with the achievements of the past year and the work we have accomplished on behalf of the arctic research community and NSF. We look forward to continuing to work with NSF and the arctic research community on these important initiatives. If you have any questions, please feel free to contact me.

Sincerely,

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read "Helen V. Wiggins".

Helen V. Wiggins

**Arctic Research Consortium of the U.S. (ARCUS)
Providing Organizational Support to the U.S. Arctic Science Program**

Year 2 Program Plan and Progress Report of Cooperative Agreement ARC-0618885
Revised

Planned activities cover the period: 1 January–31 December 2009 (Year 2 of CA);
Accomplishments cover the period: 1 April 2008 (beginning of Year 1) –31 December 2008

This document describes the program plan and progress report for the second year of ARCUS' five-year Cooperative Agreement, ARC-0618885, to provide organizational support to the NSF OPP Division of Arctic Sciences to develop, promote, and implement arctic research and education activities. The program plan and progress report summarizes accomplishments to-date (1 April 2008–present), future plans (1 January–31 December 2009), and any major changes in direction and/or pace. The budget report is included at the end of this document. The narrative organizes activities into four main task categories:

1. **Arctic Community Science Planning** – coordinating science planning for the arctic research community across disciplinary and organizational boundaries; includes SEARCH Coordination, Arctic Data Coordination, and State of the Arctic Conference activities.
2. **Coordination Support for NSF Division of Arctic Sciences Programs** – specific coordination and support for the OPP Division of Arctic Sciences programs; includes ARCSS Program Coordination, Arctic Natural Science Program Coordination, Arctic Social Sciences Program Coordination, and Arctic Section Science Materials.
3. **Arctic Science Education** – development and coordination of arctic-focused educational activities; includes Arctic Science Education Activities and the Arctic Visiting Speakers' Series.
4. **Information and Outreach** – information and outreach activities; includes *Witness the Arctic* newsletter, Website and Internet Resources, ArcticInfo listserv, Directory of Arctic Researchers, Internet Media Archive, and Arctic Community Outreach.

An additional fifth category is the provision of core support for ARCUS' NSF-funded activities—dedicated funding of the costs incurred by program activities that simultaneously support multiple cooperative agreement projects.

1. ARCTIC COMMUNITY SCIENCE PLANNING

1.1 SEARCH Coordination

The Study of Environmental Arctic Change (SEARCH) is an interagency effort to understand the nature, extent, and future development of the system-scale change presently seen in the Arctic. As the SEARCH Project Office, ARCUS works closely with the SEARCH Science Steering Committee (SSC); the Observing Change (OCP), Understanding Change (UCP), and Responding to Change (RCP) Panels; *ad hoc* working groups; and Interagency Program Management Committee (IPMC) members to coordinate SEARCH science planning, implementation, and outreach activities. In this upcoming program year, SEARCH activities will increase in preparation for an Understanding Change workshop in summer, for activities related to improved coordination of Observing, Understanding, and Responding activities, and planned changes in the SEARCH and ARCSS community planning structures. The State of the Arctic Conference planning is discussed as a separate item in section 1.3, in order to keep track of those costs and activities as a discrete activity.

Accomplishments:

Activities in the past program year of this CA focused on producing the final report from the Arctic Observation Integration Workshops, launching and implementing the SEARCH Sea Ice Outlook, SEARCH SSC activities, coordination with relevant national and international efforts, SEARCH representation at relevant meetings, ongoing planning discussions, and website updates:

- A. **Arctic Observation Integration Workshops Report** – Following on the Arctic Observation Integration Workshops, held 17–20 March 2008 in Palisades, NY (see <http://www.arcus.org/search/Meetings/2008/aow/index.php>), worked with the workshop co-chairs to draft, edit, incorporate participant input, and complete the workshop report, which was finalized in May 2008 and published online at: <http://www.arcus.org/search/meetings/2008/aow/report.php>. Printed copies were distributed to workshop participants and are available by request. The recommendations in the *Arctic Observation Integration Workshops Report* summarize short- and long-term activities to address three key challenges (1) integrating different observation efforts into a system that serves science as well as broader society and key stakeholder groups, (2) understanding the extraordinary seasonal retreat of sea ice observed in 2007, and (3) identifying scientific and programmatic gaps and next steps for observing, understanding, and responding to arctic environmental change with emphasis on high-amplitude, unexpected changes.
- B. **2008 Sea Ice Outlook Effort** – In response to a key recommendation that emerged from the Arctic Observation Integration Workshops, worked with the SSC Chair and workshop participants to launch the 2008 Sea Ice Outlook and provided “Central Office” functions for the effort (see website at: <http://www.arcus.org/search/seaiceoutlook/index.php>). Led by Jim Overland of the NOAA Pacific Marine Environmental Laboratory, the Sea Ice Outlook is an international effort to provide an integrated, community-wide summary of the state of arctic sea ice over the summer season. The organizational structure of the Sea Ice Outlook includes: a Core Integration Group (CIG), led by Jim Overland, which

integrates and synthesizes community contributions for each monthly outlook report and produces outlook products; an Advisory Group (AG) that reviews the outlook products before release and fosters broad international participation in the effort; and a Central Office (the SEARCH Project Office at ARCUS) that works with the CIG and AG to plan and implement activities, edit monthly reports, produce content for and maintain the Sea Ice Outlook website, and conduct broader outreach activities (see examples of media coverage at: http://www.arcus.org/search/sealiceoutlook/media_coverage.php). Organized an open community meeting held 17 December 2008 in conjunction with the American Geophysical Union (AGU) meeting to discuss lessons learned from the 2008 Outlook and discuss planning for a 2009 Sea Ice Outlook.

Over the 2008 season, 22 research groups contributed to the Sea Ice Outlook by providing information on current and expected states of the arctic sea ice for the monthly outlook reports. The 2008 Outlook showed good agreement between outlook projections and observations, provided a successful forum for community synthesis, and was an important initial step toward better understanding of arctic sea ice loss. A summary report of the outcomes of the 2008 Sea Ice Outlook is available at: http://www.arcus.org/search/sealiceoutlook/summary_report.php.

- C. **SEARCH Science Steering Committee (SSC) Meeting** – Organized and convened the annual SEARCH SSC meeting, held 28–30 October 2008 in Arlington, VA. This SSC meeting, attended by 31 SSC members, agency personnel, and other program representatives, focused on advancing full SEARCH implementation—assessing current activities that meet SEARCH science priorities, identifying gaps that remain, prioritizing science needs, and identifying mechanisms for further implementation, including ways to address the “Understanding Change” and “Responding to Change” components. The meeting agenda, presentations, participant list, and briefing book materials are available through the meeting webpages at: <http://www.arcus.org/search/meetings/2008/ssc/index.php>.

D. **Coordination with Relevant National and International Efforts**

SEARCH for DAMOCLES (S4D) – The SEARCH for DAMOCLES (S4D) partnership was established through a Memorandum of Understanding (MOU) between SEARCH and the European Union-funded Developing Arctic Modeling and Observing Capabilities for Long-term Environmental Studies (DAMOCLES) project. S4D aims to build on the strength of both programs to provide enhanced and coordinated acquisition of pan-arctic data sets, dissemination of results, and public awareness. ARCUS provided organizational support to the S4D international steering committee and the five S4D working groups. Specific activities in the first program year included:

- i. Provided travel support for Matt Berman, SEARCH Understanding Change Panel co-chair, to attend a Human Impacts S4D Workshop, held 15–16 September 2008 in Oslo, Norway (workshop website at: http://www.oasys-research.de/S4D_Oslo/S4D_Oslo_background).
- ii. Assisted in planning and preparations for a S4D Steering Committee meeting of opportunity in conjunction with the DAMOCLES General Assembly, held 25–28 November 2008 in Poland. Provided travel support for Peter Schlosser, SEARCH SSC Chair, and Jim Overland, Sea Ice Outlook lead and Understanding Change Panel

- member (General Assembly meeting website at: http://www.damocles-eu.org/Meetings_and_events_40/General_assembly.shtml).
- iii. Coordinated remote participation of Jean-Claude Gascard, DAMOCLES lead, in the fall 2008 SEARCH SSC Meeting.

E. SEARCH Participation in Relevant Conferences

- i. *AAAS* – As follow-up to discussions at the Arctic Observation Workshops, participated at a session on "Terrestrial Response to Rapid Climate Change in the Arctic" and other SEARCH-relevant sessions, during the AAAS 2008 Arctic Science Conference, 15–17 September in Fairbanks, AK.
- ii. *SAON* – Provided travel support for Peter Schlosser, SEARCH SSC Chair, to represent SEARCH at the Sustaining Arctic Observing Networks (SAON) 3rd Workshop, held 15–17 October 2008 in Helsinki, Finland (<http://www.arcticobserving.org/>).
- iii. *AGU* – Provided coordination support and content development for SEARCH activities at the 2008 Fall AGU Meeting, 15–19 December in San Francisco, CA, including a SEARCH poster session, a SEARCH Sea Ice Outlook talk, a meeting of the SEARCH Observing Change Panel, and other small meetings of opportunity.

F. Initial Planning for the State of the Arctic Conference – Continued discussions with SSC Chair, SSC members, and NSF on planning for State of the Arctic Conference, now scheduled for early Winter 2010.

G. Planning Teleconferences – Convened approximately monthly SEARCH planning teleconferences with SSC Chair. Assisted in coordination and preparation of Observing Panel teleconferences.

H. SEARCH Website – Ongoing website updates, maintenance, and development, including monthly Sea Ice Outlook reports, and information on meetings and workshops.

Planned Activities:

A. State of the Arctic Conference – The State of the Arctic Conference, a major SEARCH-driven activity, is discussed separately in section 1.3, below, in order to keep track of those costs and activities as a discrete activity.

B. Sea Ice Outlook – Continue the Sea Ice Outlook activities begun with the successful 2008 Sea Ice Outlook effort. (see <http://www.arcus.org/search/seaiceoutlook/index.php>).

- i. *Retrospective Working Group Meeting* – A small meeting (15–20 people) will be held 10–11 March 2009 at NSDIC in Boulder, CO, to undertake a retrospective analysis of the 2008 effort and produce a final retrospective report for 2008, with recommendations for improvements for the 2009 Sea Ice Outlook. Specific activities will include:
 - Work with the Sea Ice Outlook co-chairs (Jim Overland and Hajo Eicken), the Core Integration Group (CIG), and the Advisory Group (AG) to develop the focus, agenda, and invited participants for the meeting.

- Develop and maintain a workshop website, including overview and background information, agenda, PowerPoint presentations, participant list, and other relevant materials.
 - Provide travel support for 5–6 participants who do not have travel funding through other means, as appropriate; specific supported participants to be determined with the SIO co-chairs and the SSC Chair. Provide partial venue support (catering costs only; meeting room will be provided by NSDIC).
 - Convene an open pre-workshop eMeeting to involve the broader community in the final retrospective analysis and plans for the 2009 Sea Ice Outlook.
 - Work with meeting participants to produce the final meeting report, which will be circulated to the broader community for comment. The final report will be posted as a PDF on the Sea Ice Outlook website; a limited digital printing of 100 copies will be produced; additional copies would be printed on demand.
- ii. *Planning and Implementation of the 2009 Sea Ice Outlook* – Building on the success of the 2008 Sea Ice Outlook, the 2009 Sea Ice Outlook will provide a community-wide synthesis and monthly outlook on the state of the arctic sea ice throughout summer 2009. Through discussions with the CIG, AG, the SEARCH SSC, and wider community feedback, several improvements will be incorporated into the 2009 planning and effort, including a quicker turnaround of monthly reports and a stronger education and outreach component. The 2009 activities also will incorporate improvements as determined through the spring retrospective working group meeting. The first monthly outlook report will be released in late May 2009, with online reports released on a monthly basis until the arctic sea ice minimum (likely September 2009), and a retrospective analysis completed after the end of the season. An online summary report of the season will provide a discussion of the season, Outlook results, and lessons learned.
- C. **Develop SEARCH-ARCSS Understanding Effort** – Work with the SEARCH SSC, ARCSS Committee, and NSF Program Director to merge relevant ARCSS science activities with the SEARCH Program structure through the “Understanding Change” component. As currently structured, the SEARCH and ARCSS Programs overlap in many areas of scientific focus—both programs focus on change in the Arctic and understanding the arctic system via inter- and multi-disciplinary approaches. This overlapping science focus has led to discussions in the community and with NSF regarding merging the science planning process and organizational structure of the two programs. A new joint Understanding Change effort would reduce overlap and strengthen a shared community science planning process, while building on the intellectual pool and energy found in both communities. This idea was generally endorsed by the SEARCH SSC at the October 2008 SSC meeting, and also by the Chair of the ARCSS Committee. The specific focus, goals, objectives, and committee structure of this combined effort would be determined over the next several months with the SEARCH and ARCSS Communities, NSF, and with broad community input. Activities in this program year will include: supporting “joint” SEARCH-ARCSS teleconferences and/or eMeetings, as needed, with joint SEARCH-ARCSS committee members, drafting relevant materials and documents, and communicating to the broader community on activities via the

SEARCH and ARCSS websites and appropriate electronic mailing lists. The first activity will be a teleconference with the SEARCH SSC Chair, ARCSS Committee Chair, and NSF Program Director, to be scheduled for late February 2009. The Understanding Change workshop (see item D below) is envisioned as a key community activity that will be convened to determine the specific science goals and focus of this effort.

- D. Understanding Change Workshop** – Work with the SEARCH organizational structure, NSF program director, IPMC, and others to organize and convene an "Understanding Change Workshop" in summer (May/June) 2009. This workshop was recommended by the SEARCH SSC to present and discuss recent developments and needs for the Understanding Change component of SEARCH, including incorporation of ARCSS science. This workshop is envisioned as being relatively small, with about 30–50 participants. Science topics explored will include: model-based assimilation of available observations; improvement and expansion of model capabilities; model simulations for forecasting and for guiding observing system design; development and use of proxy records; paleo reconstructions; diagnostic analyses of synthesized observations and paleo reconstructions; studies of interactions between arctic environmental, socioeconomic and cultural changes; and topics related to advancing our scientific knowledge of the system processes involved in arctic environmental change. Specific activities in the upcoming program year will include:
- i. Convene an Organizing Committee and work with the committee on workshop goals and objectives, agenda, and participant list.
 - ii. Secure a workshop venue and work with the venue to provide meeting room arrangements; secure sleeping room block for meeting participants.
 - iii. Develop and maintain a workshop website, including agenda, background materials, and participant list.
 - iv. Work with the Organizing Committee and meeting participants to draft and finalize the workshop report, which will be posted on the SEARCH website as a PDF. A limited printing of 100 copies will be produced.
 - v. Travel support for SSC members and other key participants.
- E. Science Steering Committee (SSC) Meetings** – Convene two SEARCH SSC meetings, tentatively planned as one eMeeting, and one in-person meeting in conjunction with the Understanding Change workshop (D, above). Specific planned activities in this program year will include: determine dates and location(s) of meetings; work with SSC Chair, members, and NSF Program Director on an agenda and background materials; create meeting webpages; venue and travel support for the face-to-face meeting will be provided in conjunction with the Understanding Change workshop.
- F. SEARCH Project Catalog** – As requested by the OCP and UCP Chairs, work with the OCP, UCP, and IPMC to perform an initial assessment of current funded SEARCH projects and enter them into the online SEARCH Project Catalog. The SEARCH Project Catalog will provide an easy-to-use means for the SEARCH organizational structure, agencies, and scientists to discover SEARCH implementation status and funded projects, with links to other relevant databases as appropriate (e.g., CADIS, ARMAP, etc.). The effort undertaken in this program year will incorporate core projects and activities,

including AON (through a link to CADIS), BEST, SBI, ARCSS, and key efforts from agencies other than NSF that have self-identified as contributions to SEARCH (e.g., USFWS “Wildlife Response to Arctic Change” activities).

- G. **SEARCH Interagency Meeting** – As requested by the OCP Chair, assist the OCP in providing input to a SEARCH interagency meeting, tentatively planned for March or April 2009. OCP members Craig Lee and Peter Murdoch are leading the planning for this workshop. Specific activities will include: assisting the OCP in agenda development and participant invitations, creation of meeting webpages, and assisting with the development of workshop product(s). No logistical support activities or costs for this workshop are planned under this Cooperative Agreement year.
- H. **AON PI Meeting** – As requested by the OCP Chair, assist the OCP in providing OCP input to the planning of the 2009 annual AON PI meeting, through teleconferences, input to the agenda and participant list, and other relevant planning activities. Website support could be provided, if needed. No logistical support activities or costs for this meeting are planned under this Cooperative Agreement.
- I. **SSC and Panel Support** – Support SEARCH SSC and Panel activities, including organizing and planning teleconferences, development of relevant drafts and materials, website content development, and other support as needed.
- J. **Coordination with Relevant International Efforts** – Explore continued partnership activities with DAMOCLES, including participation in DAMOCLES General Assembly and coordination activities. Assist the SEARCH SSC chair and ISAC to develop an MOU with ArcticNet (<http://www.arcticnet.ulaval.ca/>) to facilitate coordination between overlapping activities of the two programs. Assist International Study of Arctic Change (ISAC) Chair in distributing draft ISAC Science Plan to SEARCH SSC and panel members for input in spring 2009. Provide travel support for the SEARCH SSC Chair or designated SEARCH representative to two (2) international meetings.
- K. **Other Travel Support for SSC Chair and/or Key SEARCH Representatives** – Provide travel support to the SSC Chair and/or key SEARCH representatives to key arctic meetings for invited SEARCH presentations and sessions, as appropriate.
- L. **SEARCH Website** – Ongoing website updates, maintenance, and development.

Major Changes in Direction/Pace:

An increase in SEARCH activities from the prior program year is expected as a result of SEARCH SSC, Panel, and community priorities for activities to be completed in this year.

1.2 Arctic Data Coordination

A clear need has emerged through a number of arctic planning activities, conferences, and meetings for improved arctic data coordination and management across disciplines, research programs, and agencies, with activities that capitalize on developments in cyberinfrastructure concepts and tools. Year 1 of the Cooperative Agreement focused on continued discussions with the community regarding implementation strategies for the Arctic Synthesis Collaboratory, a cyber-enabled virtual organization to advance our understanding of the arctic system.

Accomplishments:

- A. **Arctic Synthesis Collaboratory Implementation** – Community planning discussions regarding data management and coordination have increasingly focused on a conceptual framework that would advance the integration of knowledge to answer questions about how the Arctic functions as an integrated system. These community discussions, including a major planning workshop in April 2007, culminated in recommendations for the development of an Arctic Synthesis Collaboratory (see: http://www.arcus.org/arcss/message_050707.html). The Arctic Synthesis Collaboratory is envisioned an “umbrella” structure that fosters interactions among arctic scientists and other stakeholders; integrates data analysis and modeling activities; provides outreach, education, and policy-relevant resources; and offers training and professional development for the arctic science community. With continued discussions in the community regarding Collaboratory implementation, the Collaboratory leads submitted a pre-proposal to the NSF Science and Technology Centers (STC): Integrative Partnerships program solicitation (<http://www.nsf.gov/pubs/2008/nsf08580/nsf08580.htm>); the pre-proposal was submitted and the team was invited to submit a full proposal. Work for the proposal submission is not funded under this Cooperative Agreement, but is relevant to many aspects of arctic data coordination and other arctic program activities; continued discussions with the broader community on Collaboratory priorities and needs will be ongoing.
- B. **GIS of Arctic Observation Activities** – Followed-up on initial development of the Geographic Information System (GIS) of U.S. observing activities that was created for the U.S. Interagency Arctic Research Policy Committee (IARPC) report *Arctic Observing Network (AON): Toward a U.S. Contribution to Pan-Arctic Observing*. Continued development of Federal Geographic Data Committee–compliant metadata documentation of GIS layers.

Planned Activities:

- A. **GIS of Arctic Observation Activities** – Follow-up on initial development of the Geographic Information System (GIS) of U.S. observing activities that was created for the U.S. Interagency Arctic Research Policy Committee (IARPC) report “Arctic Observing Network (AON): Toward a US Contribution to Pan-Arctic Observing”:
- i. Finish development of basic metadata documentation for the GIS layers and produce a short final report of the project; final metadata report is expected by May 2009.

- ii. Initiate discussion with IARPC, NSF, and relevant groups (SEARCH SSC, etc.), on if and how the GIS may be developed as an effective community science planning tool for SEARCH and other relevant efforts.

Major Changes in Direction/Pace:

The completion of the IARPC GIS metadata was delayed due to competing demands on staff time. The *ad hoc* arctic data working group originally proposed will not be pursued at this time as a separate CA activity, until such time that NSF activities present clear objectives for arctic data coordination efforts. Informal discussions with arctic data groups will continue as part of relevant program activities (e.g., SEARCH). Plans for an implementation-focused Collaboratory workshop will be postponed until the results of the Collaboratory STC proposal are known (accept/decline notices are expected August 2009).

1.3 State of the Arctic Conference

Planned Activities:

Planning for the Winter 2010 State of the Arctic Conference—The State of the Arctic Conference (SoA) is envisioned as a community-wide forum to present, exchange, and discuss the latest knowledge of the state of the Arctic—its physical, natural, biological, and human components, including response strategies—with the goal of providing guidance for the future of arctic research. The conference will be held in the U.S., with major international participation; approximately 1,000 participants are expected to attend. See Appendix A, State of the Arctic Conference Prospectus, for more details about the purpose and goal of the conference. Activities within this program year related to the SoA will focus on planning and organizational activities for a conference to be held early 2010; the exact dates will be determined by venue availability and to avoid community conflicts as best as possible. All planning activities will be done in collaboration with the SEARCH SSC Chair, SSC, Panels, IPMC, other relevant programs (e.g., ARCSS), and relevant NSF Program Managers. Specific activities in this program year will include:

- i. Convene a conference Organizing Committee (OC); facilitate OC planning teleconferences and/or eMeetings (one monthly then in increasing frequency as conference planning proceeds, and/or as needed). The OC will be convened in collaboration with the SEARCH SSC; committee members will be selected to represent broad disciplinary, programmatic, and agency input; the OC should be convened with a committee charge in March 2009.
- ii. Secure a venue and date of conference; venues will be researched and assessed based on price, availability, facilities, and location. Work with the venue to arrange meeting space needs and work with nearby hotel(s) to secure sleeping room blocks at meeting rates (most participants will pay for their own arrangements).
- iii. Work with the OC to develop goals and objectives of conference.
- iv. Work with the OC to develop the agenda, including overall structure of the conference and sessions, session content and flow, talk topics, and invited and accepted speakers.
- v. Explore, in collaboration with the SEARCH organizational structure, co-sponsorship from relevant national and international programs, organizations, and agencies.

- vi. Develop and maintain a conference website, which will include overall background information, agenda materials, registration pages, abstracts, and other related resources.
- vii. Manage an online presentation and/or poster abstract submission process.
- viii. Develop and distribute announcements and other outreach materials.
- ix. Provide travel support for a limited number of participants, including SSC Chair and invited speakers.

Costs for the State of the Arctic Conference will be split between this program year, in which the majority of planning will occur, and the next program year, in which the conference will take place.

2. NSF ARCTIC SCIENCES SECTION COORDINATION

2.1 ARCSS Program Coordination

The Arctic System Science (ARCSS) Program addresses the physical, chemical, biological, and social processes of the Arctic and how these arctic systems interact with the Earth as a whole, including changes in the arctic system and their global ramifications. ARCUS provides community science management and coordination of activities for the NSF Arctic System Science Program and serves as the ARCSS Science Management Office (SMO). Program coordination activities are designed to sustain an effective system-science effort and foster high levels of community input and strong interdisciplinary collaboration.

2.1.1 ARCSS Coordination

Accomplishments:

- A. **ARCSS Committee Coordination** – Convened two ARCSS Committee teleconferences to discuss ARCSS planning and convened approximately monthly calls with the ARCSS Committee chair. Discussions primarily focused on issues related to the development of the “Seasonality Effort” (see item B, below).
- B. **eTown Meeting on “Seasonality” Effort** – Through focused community discussions over the past few years, the role of seasonality in the changing arctic system emerged as a key unknown and a science priority in the ARCSS community. In early June 2008, NSF announced a solicitation for research on Changing Seasonality in the Arctic System (CSAS): http://www.nsf.gov/funding/pgm_summ.jsp?pims_id=503195). To help ensure this new research effort is conceptually well-integrated into the larger ARCSS Program, planned and implemented an open community eTown Meeting to provide a forum for the community to discuss seasonality science and connections to the arctic system; held on 19 August 2008 with 60 participants (http://www.arcus.org/arcss/etm/august_08/index.html).
- C. **Ongoing Website Maintenance and Development** – Continued updates, maintenance, and development of the ARCSS website.
- D. **Subawards** – Subawards to support activities of the HARC Core Office at the University of Alaska Fairbanks and ARCSS Committee chair at University of California Santa Barbara (UCSB) through 31 December 2008.

The subaward to UCSB supported the activities and contributions of Dr. Joshua Schimel. Dr. Schimel chairs the ARCSS Committee (AC). Dr. Schimel worked with ARCUS to plan and carry out a range of other activities related to ARCSS Program planning and community leadership, including AC teleconferences, community eTown Meetings on specific topics, and other community science management or science planning activities as needed.

Accomplishments of the subaward to the University of Alaska Fairbanks to support the HARC Core Office are included in Appendix B.

Planned Activities:

- A. **Merge ARCSS and SEARCH Understanding Change Efforts** – Work with ARCSS Committee, NSF Program Director, and SEARCH SSC to merge ARCSS research with SEARCH Program Structure, for activities related to the SEARCH “Understanding Change” Component, as appropriate. As discussed in section 1.1.C., above, discussions are ongoing to combine aspects of ARCSS community planning activities with SEARCH Understanding Change planning activities. The ARCSS Committee will further discuss their recommendations and perspective, as representatives of the ARCSS community, on this proposed effort and will work with the SEARCH SSC and NSF to help guide the strategic planning decisions in the next several months. Specific activities in this program year will include: supporting “joint” SEARCH-ARCSS teleconferences and/or eMeetings as needed with joint SEARCH-ARCSS committee members, drafting relevant materials and documents, and communicating to the broader community on activities via the SEARCH and ARCSS websites and appropriate mailing lists.
- B. **ARCSS Committee Meetings** – As the SEARCH and ARCSS Understanding efforts merge, the ARCSS Committee will continue ARCSS Committee teleconferences and eMeetings, as appropriate, until such time a new committee structure is in place. Approximately 4–6 teleconferences will be planned. An in-person ARCSS Committee meeting will be held at the Understanding Change workshop (see also SEARCH section, above). Specific activities in this program year will include: work with the ARCSS Committee on teleconference and meeting agendas and background materials; create meeting webpages with the agenda, participant lists, presentations, and other materials; and provide travel support for Committee members and venue/meeting room arrangements for the face-to-face meeting. The subaward to the ARCSS Committee chair will not be continued in 2009, in favor of a smaller stipend for time devoted to leading ARCSS Committee activities.
- C. **HARC Subaward** – Funds continued from 2008 (no new funds are requested) will be used by HARC to complete a Synthesis Report summarizing ten years of HARC research, priorities for research (near, medium, and long-term), assessment of state of human dimensions research within arctic science, and a bibliography of HARC research publications. This document also will include a long-term vision/strategic plan to ensure continued and increased proposal pressure and to facilitate community awareness of opportunities for national, international, and interdisciplinary collaborative research and scholarly development in human dimensions research in the arctic. A draft of the report will be made available for public comment in early spring 2009. The final report will be made available online as a PDF and distributed via the HARC website and relevant mailing lists, with a small printing of the Executive Summary.

Major Changes in Direction/Pace:

The HARC Synthesis Report was not completed in 2008 due to competing demands of HARC Core Office staff time.

2.2 Arctic Natural Sciences Program Coordination

The Arctic Natural Sciences (ANS) Program is a multidisciplinary program within the NSF Division of Arctic Sciences that supports research in the atmospheric, biological, and earth sciences; glaciology; and oceanography. ARCUS will continue to coordinate ANS science planning activities related to the Bering Sea, a region that is ecologically diverse and economically and culturally important.

Accomplishments:

ARCUS coordinated a Town Hall meeting for the Arctic Natural Sciences Program on 16 December 2008 in conjunction with the AGU Fall Meeting (see announcement at: http://siempre.arcus.org/4DACTION/wi_ai_getArcticInfo/3871); topics discussed included portfolio balance, the proposal review process, recent budget impacts and responses, and other competitions of interest to the Arctic Natural Sciences community.

Planned Activities:

None.

Major Changes in Direction/Pace:

None.

2.2.1 Bering Sea Research Coordination

Since March 2003, ARCUS has provided the Arctic Natural Sciences Program with organizational support and coordination of activities for the Bering Ecosystem Study (BEST) science planning process. BEST priorities for research were included in the Fall 2005 NSF Arctic Sciences Section Announcement of Opportunity (<http://www.nsf.gov/pubs/2005/nsf05618/nsf05618.htm>) and in a special program solicitation in December 2006 (http://www.nsf.gov/publications/pub_summ.jsp?ods_key=nsf07533); awards through these opportunities were announced in July 2006 and September 2007. The funded BEST projects are the NSF contribution to a special research partnership with the North Pacific Research Board (NPRB) to support a comprehensive, vertically integrated investigation of the ecosystem of the eastern continental shelf of the Bering Sea. As the program moved into implementation, ARCUS provided organizational support to its joint Science Advisory Board (SAB) and coordination with other organizations, principally NPRB and the developing Alaska Ocean Observing System (AOOS).

Accomplishments:

- A. **Joint Science Advisory Board** – Coordinated and supported travel for three (3) BEST PIs to Washington, D.C., for a meeting of the Science Advisory Board held 5–6 June 2008.
- B. **PI Meeting** – Supported travel and participation of one (1) ARCUS staff member to the annual PI meeting held 14–16 October 2008 in Girdwood, AK, for meeting support (see meeting website at: <http://bsierp.nprb.org/meetings/annual.html>).

- C. **PI Teleconferences** – ARCUS staff participated in monthly PI teleconferences to stay abreast of program developments.
- D. **Miscellaneous Travel Support** – Coordinated and supported travel for one (1) Science Advisory Board member to represent the program at the Ecosystem of Subarctic Seas (ESSAS) workshops and Science Steering Committee meeting held 15–19 September in Halifax, Canada.
- E. **Planning for Arctic Workshop at 2009 Alaska Marine Science Symposium** – As part of the 2009 Alaska Marine Science Symposium in Anchorage, AK, NPRB led a workshop on marine research and monitoring efforts in the Arctic, particularly in the Beaufort and Chukchi Seas. The goal of this workshop, held on 23 January 2009, was to share information and promote collaboration among the many entities with increasing activities in marine research and monitoring in the region, including the oil and gas industry, local, state, and federal agencies, and non-governmental and academic organizations. The workshop also included a panel discussion of stakeholder issues and needs in the region. This workshop was an initial step toward the longer term development of a more comprehensive monitoring and assessment plan, through which each participating organization can focus on projects to meet their particular goals while contributing to a larger data sharing and integration effort. An ARCUS project manager served on the workshop organizing committee; participated in monthly planning teleconferences since June 2008; and attended the workshop to participate in planning discussions, present relevant posters, and gave a presentation on AON activities in the Beaufort and Chukchi Seas. The workshop website is available at: <http://www.alaskamarinescience.org/>.
- F. **HBEST Science Plan** – Completed initial editing, graphics selection, and publication design for the HBEST (Humans-BEST) Science Plan, “*Sustaining the Bering Sea Ecosystem: A Social Sciences Research Plan*,” as a parallel plan to the BEST Science Plan. The HBEST Science Plan seeks to initiate research to elucidate the dynamic relationship between humans and the Bering Sea ecosystem.

Planned Activities:

- A. **Joint Science Advisory Board (SAB)** – Coordinate and support travel for three (3) BEST PIs to Washington, D.C. for the 2009 meeting of the SAB (dates TBD).
- B. **PI Meeting** – Support travel and participation of one (1) ARCUS staff member to the annual PI meeting planned for October 2009 in Girdwood, AK, for meeting support.
- C. **PI teleconferences and eMeetings** – ARCUS staff will participate in monthly PI teleconferences to stay abreast of program developments. If requested by program leadership, support three (3) online eMeetings for research coordination and planning.
- D. **Miscellaneous Travel Support** – Travel support to address program goals, as needed.

- E. **Development of Arctic Monitoring and Assessment Plan for Beaufort and Chukchi Seas** – ARCUS is participating in a planning process led by the North Pacific Research Board and Alaska Ocean Observing System on marine research and monitoring efforts in the Arctic, particularly in the Beaufort and Chukchi seas. ARCUS served on the organizing committee for a recent Arctic Workshop, held 23 January 2009 in conjunction with the Alaska Marine Science Symposium, that enabled the many entities with increasing activities in marine research and monitoring in the region, including the oil and gas industry, local, state, and federal agencies, and non-governmental and academic organizations, to share information and promoted collaboration; the workshop also included a panel discussion of stakeholder issues and needs in the region (see Appendix C for more information). ARCUS will continue to participate in the planning process toward longer term development of a more comprehensive monitoring and assessment plan, through which each participating organization can focus on projects to meet their particular goals while contributing to a larger data sharing and integration effort. Specific activities will include participation in teleconferences and contributions to draft documents and related materials.
- F. **HBEST Science Plan** – Final editing, publication, and distribution in fall 2009 of the HBEST (Humans-BEST) Science Plan, “*Sustaining the Bering Sea Ecosystem: A Social Sciences Research Plan*,” as a parallel plan to the BEST Science Plan. The HBEST Science Plan seeks to initiate research to elucidate the dynamic relationship between humans and the Bering Sea ecosystem. The plan outlines a research program focused on three themes:
- Impacts on humans: How past, current, and possible future changes in the Bering Sea ecosystem affect the health and wellbeing of human communities living and depending on this region for subsistence, employment, and cultural survival.
 - Human impacts: How changing human uses of the Bering Sea region affect the natural cycles of this ecosystem by moderating and/or accelerating systemic changes.
 - Dynamics of human and non-human natural systems: How the human-environmental dynamic has changed through time and may change in the future due to internal and external opportunities and pressures.

Major Changes in Direction/Pace:

Final editing, publication, and distribution of the HBEST Science Plan was delayed due to competing demands on staff time.

2.3 Arctic Social Sciences Program Coordination

The Arctic Social Sciences Program (ASSP) is a multidisciplinary and interdisciplinary program that encompasses all social sciences research supported by NSF. The Arctic Social Sciences Program supports research that documents and analyzes the dynamic cultures, economies, and technologies of northern populations.

2.3.1 Arctic Social Sciences Coordination

Accomplishments:

No activities were planned for this year.

Planned Activities:

No activities planned in this year.

Major Changes in Direction/Pace:

None.

2.4.1 Arctic Section Science Materials

ARCUS, in collaboration with NSF program staff, will develop information and communication resources such as posters and brochures that reach across geographic, cultural, institutional, and disciplinary barriers to assist planning and integration of diverse research efforts and to improve awareness of NSF-sponsored research in the Arctic.

Accomplishments:

No activities completed for this year.

Planned Activities:

Update the Arctic Discoveries Poster – Work with NSF to update, as needed, the *Arctic Discoveries* poster for use as an NSF outreach tool.

Major Changes in Direction/Pace:

None.

3. ARCTIC SCIENCE EDUCATION

3.1 Arctic Science Education Activities

ARCUS will continue to provide an educational leadership role within the arctic community through activities designed to bridge arctic research and education.

Accomplishments:

- A. **SACNAS Researcher Travel Scholarship** – Organized and coordinated a travel grant competition for interested arctic researchers or students to participate in networking and mentoring opportunities at the Society for Advancement of Chicanos and Native Americans in Science (SACNAS) Annual National Conference held 9–12 October 2008 in Salt Lake City, UT; the theme of the 2008 meeting was International Polar Year: Global Change in Our Communities (<http://www.arcus.org/education/sacnas/index.html>). Provided partial travel support for nine (9) applicants, ranging from senior research faculty to science teachers to undergraduates, who participated in a variety of activities at the meeting, including judging student presentations and networking and outreach at the ARCUS conference booth.
- B. **International Polar Year Focus Days** – In collaboration with the IPY International Program Office, organized and hosted quarterly live events for a broad audience on International Polar Days. Topics included "Changing Earth", "Land & Life", and "Above the Poles;" events involved researchers working in both polar regions. More than 750 individuals, primarily K-12 students from North America, participated in the three events.
- C. **Extreme Cold Weather Gear kit** – Collected and made available on request a kit of Extreme Cold Weather Gear for use in educating students and the public about the realities of polar research. Publicized the kit's availability to a wide audience and distributed kit for use at 15 local or national education events.
- D. **"Learning from Our Place"** – In collaboration with the University of Alaska Fairbanks and Alaska Bird Observatory, organized and conducted a polar literacy training session for Alaska classroom teachers in April 2008. More than 20 teachers participated.

Planned Activities:

- A. Provide support for one K-12 science teacher to attend the PolarTREC Orientation and ShareFair, 23–27 February in Fairbanks, Alaska, to facilitate connections with underrepresented students.
- B. Arctic science education and outreach activities, to be determined with the program officer, as opportunities arise.

Major Changes in Direction/Pace:

None.

3.2 Arctic Visiting Speakers' Series

ARCUS initiated the Arctic Visiting Speakers' (AVS) Series in 2000 to increase communication and collaboration among the dispersed arctic research community and to nurture better understanding and communication between arctic researchers and arctic community residents (see website at: http://www.arcus.org/arctic_speaker/index.html).

Accomplishments:

AVS Tours – Continued the AVS program with two (2) AVS tours:

- In September 2008, Angaangaq Lyberth visited Montpelier, VT. Angaangaq was hosted by the non-profit organization EarthWalk Vermont. A native of Greenland, Lyberth gave workshops at various public venues and a special presentation at EarthWalk, a nonprofit community promoting nature education.
- In April 2008 Jonathan Waterman traveled to the Center for Northern Studies at Sterling College in Vermont. An author, filmmaker, and lecturer specializing in northern issues, Waterman joined Sterling classes, met with students who have read his writing as part of their coursework, and presented a free public lecture entitled "Oil Versus Wilderness and Climate Change in the Arctic National Wildlife Refuge." Waterman also spoke at the Craftsbury Academy, a local public junior/senior high school, where he discussed issues related to environmental preservation and natural resource exploration in Alaska.

Planned Activities:

AVS Tours – Continuation of current program, with support for six (6) AVS tours.

Major Changes in Direction/Pace:

The low number of AVS tours in the previous program year (Yr 1) was due to the timing of the 2008 tours; only two (2) fell within Year 1 of the CA period, which began in 1 April 2008.

4. INFORMATION AND OUTREACH

ARCUS serves as a communication channel providing information about current research activities and arctic issues to the scientific community, agencies, and the public.

4.1 *Witness the Arctic* Newsletter

Witness the Arctic is a newsletter that provides information on current arctic research and education efforts and news, significant research initiatives, national policy affecting arctic science, research support and logistics, profiles of institutions with major arctic research efforts, and calendar events and publications.

Accomplishments:

Solicited articles, edited contributions, and prepared content for publication for the 24-page annual newsletter; the feature article is "Arctic Climate Change: Where Reality Exceeds Expectations" by Mark Serreze.

Planned Activities:

Publish and distribute the winter 2008/2009 issue of *Witness the Arctic* newsletter to the 13,900 subscribers (5,300 of which are located outside the U.S.). To improve timeliness of reporting and reduce printing and mailing costs, *Witness the Arctic* will change to an online format, with two (2–4) shorter online news updates of interest to the arctic research community. Copies will be printed in-house only to send to key community members and to distribute at meetings, or as requested. For 2009, the tentative publication schedule will be May, September, and an end-of-year issue in December. Shorter “news updates” will be issued online if needed (e.g., summary of sets of newly-funded NSF projects, etc.).

Major Changes in Direction/Pace:

After this program year, costs for *Witness the Arctic* printing and shipping will decrease, as we move to online issues. This program year will contain one (1) printing, as the winter 2008/2009 printing and shipping costs will fall within this program year. Publication of the current winter 2008/2009 issue, originally planned for printing in 2008, was delayed by competing demands on staff time and is expected in March 2009.

4.2 Website and Internet Resources

The ARCUS website provides essential information and resources for the diverse and geographically distributed arctic research community and serves more than 6,000 files from over 2,000 pages. The website is the focal point for educational programs, various community science planning efforts, and provides important information and resources to the research community about research programs, meetings, community activities, and publications. Among many other resources, the website provides program information, electronic copies of publications, agenda, abstracts, and participant lists from arctic meetings, and audio and video archives from a variety of programs and meetings.

Accomplishments:

In addition to content development for a variety of specific programs and activities, many improvements to the website structure and function have been made since 2001. Users benefit from ease of use through a more intuitive interface and vastly decreased page-load times due to these changes. The ARCUS website increasingly utilizes user-driven or user-created content. This transition has been coincident with and prompted by changes in browser technology as well as standard practices of many leading websites on the World Wide Web. Data and information are dynamically served from external 4D and MySQL databases, and the site features dynamic, user-created content through simple interfaces such as message boards and forums, photo albums, and calendars.

Planned Activities:

Continue to update website, develop new content, and improve functionality, as needed. In addition, website-tracking software to analyze website use patterns (e.g., google analytics) will be increasingly utilized in order to track use and provide improvements, as appropriate.

Major Changes in Direction/Pace:

None.

4.3 ArcticInfo Listserve

ARCUS continues to develop and maintain ArcticInfo, the primary electronic mailing list for the arctic research community. ArcticInfo provides timely information about funding opportunities, important events, publications, position announcements, and other useful news. All postings are archived in a searchable directory on the ARCUS website. Submissions and subscribers to ArcticInfo have increased steadily over the past years.

Accomplishments:

Continued to develop and maintain the listserve, including receiving, editing, and posting 419 announcements to the list between 1 April and 31 December 2008; ArcticInfo currently has 6,186 current email subscribers.

Planned Activities:

Continue to develop and maintain the moderated listserve, including receiving, editing, and posting announcements to the list.

Major Changes in Direction/Pace:

None.

4.4 Directory of Arctic Researchers

The Directory of Arctic Researchers was initiated in 1994 to facilitate networking and collaboration in arctic research and education efforts between individual investigators, institutions, funding agencies, and arctic stakeholders. The contents of the Directory, which includes information on over 4,000 U.S. and international arctic researchers, are developed through surveys of individual arctic researchers and institutions (see website at: <http://www.arcus.org/researcher/index.html>).

Accomplishments:

Continued to develop and maintain the Directory of Arctic Researchers, which currently contains 4,129 individual entries.

Planned Activities:

Continue to develop and maintain the Directory of Arctic Researchers.

Major Changes in Direction/Pace:

None.

4.5 Internet Media Archive

The ARCUS Internet Media Archive (IMA) is a collection of polar-relevant photos, graphics, videos, and presentations that have been compiled for various purposes and are shared through the ARCUS website. The IMA currently contains over 6,500 public photos (4,000 from TREC and PolarTREC), 450 videos, 270 audio files, 100 graphics and logos, and 28 PowerPoint presentations.

Accomplishments:

In Yr 1, a very minor level of staff time was dedicated to the IMA, as other priorities demanded staff time. In Yr 1, 242 photos were made publicly available; 120 edited video files were added and made public, and 23 new logo files were added.

Planned Activities:

Continue to develop and maintain the IMA and work on the backlog of resources waiting to be entered into the IMA database. There are 12,000 additional resources that are currently being processed for publication in the IMA (i.e., adding keywords, attribution, permission levels, etc.). The primary improvements planned for the IMA in 2009 include importing new resources and processing the resources to allow for public access (by adding photo tags, keywords, and descriptions). A new category of resources will be added for video clips from key arctic science talks (with permission of the speakers). The IMA software will be updated as needed to increase the ease of user operation and functionality.

Major Changes in Direction/Pace:

Staff resources in Yr 1 devoted to the IMA were very minimal, as other demands required staff time. Yr 2 will contain a more standard level of staff time, in order to maintain the addition of resources into the IMA.

4.6 Arctic Community Outreach

ARCUS continues to conduct a number of outreach activities that disseminate timely information about arctic research to scientists, policy and decision-makers, educators and the public, and that build supportive networks among those groups to advance international arctic research efforts and our understanding of the Arctic.

Accomplishments:

- A. **Arctic Forum 2008** – Convened *Arctic Forum 2008* on “Tipping Points—The Arctic and Global Change,” co-chaired by Martin Miles, Environmental Systems Analysis Research Center in Boulder, Colorado, and Craig Fleener, Gwich'in Council International. The meeting was attended by 171 in-person participants from seven countries and over 65 online participants, representing an extensive array of organizations and agencies, including local, state, federal and international governments, private entities, universities, research institutions, press, and non-profit native organizations (see website at: http://www.arcus.org/annual_meetings/2008/index.html).
- B. **Arctic Community Meeting Space at AGU Fall Meeting** – Provided and organized a “Community Meeting Space” for the fall 2008 AGU Meeting to encourage scientific collaboration and to make face-to-face meetings of opportunity possible for the arctic research community. During the week of AGU, a small conference room (accommodating 20–30 people) was reserved at the San Francisco Marriott, a location central to AGU sessions. This room was available by appointment for groups working on arctic research or science education planning activities, with scheduling priority to groups directly related to NSF-funded programs. The 2008 meeting schedule can be found at: <http://www.arcus.org/communitymeetings/agu2008/aguschedule.html>.

Planned Activities:

- A. **Arctic Community Meeting Space at AGU Fall Meeting** – Provide and organize a “Community Meeting Space” for the Fall 2009 AGU Meeting to encourage scientific collaboration and to make face-to-face meetings of opportunity possible for the arctic research community. During the week of AGU, a small conference room (accommodating 20–30 people) will be reserved, tentatively at the San Francisco Marriott, a location central to AGU sessions. This room will be available by appointment for groups working on arctic research or science education planning activities, with scheduling priority to groups directly related to NSF-funded programs. ARCUS has provided this space at AGU since 2005; feedback from users of the Community Meeting Space has been overwhelmingly positive, with many comments each year on the utility of the service to advance collaboration, networking, and enhance project outcomes.
- B. **Arctic Forum 2008 Proceedings** – Finalize and publish proceedings of the *Arctic Forum 2008*, “Tipping Points—The Arctic and Global Change.” The proceedings include

presentation and poster abstracts, and summaries of panel, participant, and student discussions on priorities in arctic science and education.

- C. **Community Outreach** – outreach at AGU and other prominent arctic or related meetings and conferences, as appropriate.

Major Changes in Direction/Pace:

An *Arctic Forum* meeting will not be held in 2009, as NSF requested that it be removed from the Cooperative Agreement award. Other funding avenues will be explored for an *Arctic Forum* 2010.

5. CORE SUPPORT

5.1 Core Support

Core Support includes program activities that simultaneously support multiple cooperative agreement projects and cannot be attributed to a specific project.

Accomplishments:

Supported direct project-related activities that support all of the projects included under the NSF CA, rather than specific projects, including portions of the Executive Director, Director of Programs, and System Administrator salaries.

Planned Activities:

Continue support of direct activities that address multiple tasks and programs, including portions of the Executive Director, Director of Programs, and System Administrator salaries.

Major Changes in Direction/Pace:

None.

ARCUS Year 2 CA Timeline (1 January–31 December 2009)

ARCUS Year 2 CA Timeline (1 January–31 December 2009)

1. ARCTIC COMMUNITY SCIENCE PLANNING

1.1 SEARCH Coordination & 1.3 State of the Arctic Conference

ARCUS Year 2 CA Timeline (1 January–31 December 2009)

1. ARCTIC COMMUNITY SCIENCE PLANNING *(Continued)*

1.2 Arctic Data Coordination

ARCUS Year 2 CA Timeline (1 January–31 December 2009)

2. NSF ARCTIC SCIENCES SECTION COORDINATION

2.1 ARCSS Program Coordination

ARCUS Year 2 CA Timeline (1 January–31 December 2009)

2. NSF ARCTIC SCIENCES SECTION COORDINATION *(Continued)*

2.2.1 Arctic Natural Sciences Program Coordination: Bering Sea Research Coordination

HBEST Science Plan: Final Editing, Publication, and Distribution

2.4.1 Arctic Section Science Materials

Update the *Arctic Science Discoveries* Poster

ARCUS Year 2 CA Timeline (1 January–31 December 2009)

3. ARCTIC SCIENCE EDUCATION

3.1 Arctic Science Education Activities

JAN	FEB	MARCH	APRIL	MAY	JUNE	JULY	AUG	SEPT	OCT	NOV	DEC
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Support for teacher to PTREC
Orientation & ShareFair
(23-27 Feb)

Arctic science education and outreach activities,
to be determined with the program officer as opportunities arise.

3.2 Arctic Visiting Speakers' Series

Ongoing Tour Management (6 Tours)

ARCUS Year 2 CA Timeline (1 January–31 December 2009)

4. INFORMATION AND OUTREACH

5. CORE SUPPORT

Appendix A. State of the Arctic Conference Prospectus

State of the Arctic Conference

Prospectus

Version: 26 January 2009

Fundamental Need

The arctic science community is facing the significant challenge of studying a rapidly changing arctic system, including the human domain and socioeconomic impacts. This requires development of new ways to advance understanding of the system and consider issues related to capacity building in the scientific community. In order to meet these needs, the broad arctic science community needs a platform, i.e., an open science conference, to exchange new findings emerging from the interpretation of multi-disciplinary data sets and synthesis and modeling activities, and to engage in joint exploration of new lines of inquiry. In addition, there exists a need for a venue and opportunity in which to communicate the scientific message to stakeholders, decision makers and the general public, and to discuss strategies for response options to arctic environmental change.

Context for State of the Arctic Conference

The planned workshop would be the third in a series of meetings dating back to 1997.

The initial workshop on Arctic Change (1997; APL Seattle) was focused on the physical nature of the changes observed in the Arctic, primarily the Arctic Ocean. This workshop drew the attention of the community to the problem of system-scale changes and led to the formation of the SEARCH program.

The second, much larger meeting (SEARCH Open Science Meeting [OSM], Bell Harbor, Seattle, 2003) benefited from half a decade of new observations and a developing thought process about the nature of the observed changes, and was organized with a cross-disciplinary and multi-disciplinary focus. The SEARCH OSM had significant impact on the thinking of the community in framing the scientific questions related to system-scale changes and the requirements of a program to address these questions. It sharpened our thinking concerning the anthropogenic drivers of the signals that we saw in the Arctic at that time and challenged the community to frame the SEARCH program more solidly in the context of change rather than variability or climate modes.

An OSM session also initiated the International Study of Arctic Change (ISAC), the international program for studying change across the entire arctic system.

During the SEARCH OSM meeting, the science results from the first Arctic System Science (ARCSS) Program Synthesis Workshop (Big Sky, 2003) were incorporated into the discussions and participants' assessment of our current understanding of the Arctic. From these discussions, the idea emerged to hold a State of the Arctic Conference around 2006, in order to build on the previous and planned community activities and provide a future venue for a community-wide science meeting. The idea was promoted by the

SEARCH SSC and has been pursued in principle since then. It also has been discussed with the ARCSS Committee and received very positive response concerning co-sponsorship.

Readiness for the State of the Arctic Conference

We are now ready to bring the community together to energize, and fully engage in arctic change programs such as SEARCH, ISAC, DAMOCLES, and ArcticNet, and to rally the science community behind the three-pronged approach needed to face the challenge of arctic change: (1) observations, (2) synthesis- and model-based understanding with projections and predictions on a variety of space and time scales, and (3) designing response options such as adaptation and mitigation to change. The concepts for such programs were formulated several years ago, but the recent change in public perception concerning climate change place considerable urgency on action by the scientific community. The planned State of the Arctic conference would be the integrating and energizing mechanism for promoting and advancing a coherent and comprehensive approach. It would be the ultimate signal to the community that the environmental change programs have developed into implemented programs and hence will play a critical role in the future of arctic science. They also will capture much of the legacy of the International Polar Year (IPY) and will play a large role in underpinning SAON.

Timing

SEARCH shifted the date of the conference several times to accommodate significant events, including the IPY and the New Hampshire ASSW. We also delayed the timing of the conference back to assemble enough implemented pieces in the SEARCH program to justify such a conference. With the end of the IPY nearing, the sea ice minimum of 2007 surprising us, and the launch of ISAC behind us, we have a window of opportunity that we have to use. This window will close fast after the end of the IPY.

Considering these variables, as well as the lead-time required for logistical planning, winter 2010 appears to be the best timing for the conference, with exact dates dependent on venue availability.

International Contributions and Sponsorships

SEARCH will pursue co-sponsorship by DAMOCLES, Arctic Net, ISAC (and thus IASC), and ARCSS. SEARCH also could seek co-sponsorship directly from IASC for the conference.

Venue and Size

The conference should be held in the U.S., as most of the leading synthesis work has been driven by the U.S. community. The design of arctic change studies as a multi-dimensional and multi-disciplinary program emerged from the U.S. and is primarily implemented through SEARCH. Also, the 2009 ASSW meeting to be held in Bergen, Norway already will provide a European-based community event.

We expect approximately 1,000 participants, with significant international participation. Registration fees will be charged to offset participant costs.

Appendix B. HARC Core Office Accomplishments

HARC Core Office Accomplishments

1 April – 31 December 2008 (9-month year)

(As subaward in ARCUS Cooperative Agreement ARC-0618885)

1. **2nd Sustaining Arctic Observation Networks Workshop** – Edmonton, Canada, 9–11 April 2008. On behalf of HARC, co-chaired the chaired the Human Dimension (HD) working group follow-up session; produced the HD report.

2. **Communication Meetings** – Four (4) teleconference meetings and email discussion with the HARC SSG since January 2008 for developing the summary documents from meetings over the past three years, including follow-up from the fall synthesis meeting and for planning final activities.

3. **Arctic Forum 2008** – Participated as a panelist at the 2008 *Arctic Forum* on a panel focused on “Environmental Tipping Points” and presented a poster on HARC at the poster session.

4. **AAAS Session** - Co-organized a session at the AAAS Arctic Division Conference (15–17 September 2008) on “Terrestrial Response to Rapid Climate and Land Use Change in the Arctic.” This session included papers dealing with the linked terrestrial and human response to rapid change and the cumulative effects of rapid change in the arctic:

- Cumulative effects of rapid land-cover and land-use changes on the Yamal Peninsula, Russia. *Donald (Skip) Walker*
- Cumulative Impacts of Petroleum Development on Reindeer Herding in Northwest, Russia. *Bruce Forbes*
- Spatial patterns of NDVI distribution on the Yamal Peninsula, *Martha Reynolds*
- Cumulative Trends and Variability of Sea Ice, Land Surface Temperatures, and Vegetation in Northern Alaska. *Uma Bhatt*
- Impacts of Shifting Sea Ice Conditions on Human Settlement and Land Use in Arctic North America. *Maribeth Murray*
- St. Matthew Island: An Archive of Paleo- and Recent Ecological Change in Oceanic Beringia. *David Klein*
- Developing a Decision-support Tool for Long-term Infrastructure Planning on the North Slope of Alaska. *Larry Bright*
- The Scenarios Network for Alaska Planning: Landscape Management Collaboration and Planning in a Climate of Change. *Nancy Fresco*
- Panel Discussion
- Travel support for one (1) human dimensions researcher (Bruce Forbes)
- HARC presentation of HD research synthesis and HARC poster

5. **HARC Open Meeting and SSG Meeting at Fall 2008 AGU** – Convened two HARC meetings of opportunity at the fall 2008 AGU (held in ARCUS AGU Community Meeting Room):

- HARC Open Meeting to gather community input on directions for arctic HD research and input into draft HARC Synthesis Report.

- HARC SSG Meeting to discuss and finalize capstone HARC products and outcomes.

In addition, HARC activities at AGU included:

- Presentation of a HARC poster
- Invited HARC talk at Union Session U23

Appendix C. Chukchi and Beaufort Seas Research and Monitoring

Arctic Research and Monitoring

**Toward a Strategy for the Chukchi and Beaufort Seas
A Report and Analysis based on the January 23, 2009 Workshop
Prepared by Dr. Craig Dorman, retired University of Alaska vice-president for
Research
DRAFT**

1. Introduction.

The Alaska Ocean Observing System (AOOS) and the North Pacific Research Board (NPRB) sponsored a one-day workshop on Arctic Research and Monitoring at the end of the 2009 Alaska Marine Science Symposium, January 23, 2009. The goal of the workshop, which followed an initial Arctic Research and Monitoring Collaboration Roundtable held in the summer of 2008, was “to share information and promote collaboration among the many entities with increasing activities in marine research and monitoring in the region, including the oil and gas industry, local, state and federal agencies, and non-governmental and academic organizations.” Sessions included summaries from each of the principal research and monitoring sponsors and programs, panel discussions on data user and provider issues and needs, and synthesis presentations on past efforts and major gaps in knowledge and plans. The presentations were followed by a facilitated action group to discuss plans and recommendations for data management, logistics, synthesis, and gap analysis and a road map. The agenda, participant list, and draft action plan updated with the suggestions from the meeting are attached and are available, along with viewgraphs from all presentations, at <http://www.aos.org>.

The history of research and monitoring in the Chukchi and Beaufort Sea regions by the international science community dates back to the late 19th century. The first research station at Barrow was established during the first International Polar Year, 1882-1883. The Navy’s Arctic Research Lab was established at a Barrow oil exploration camp in 1947 and, after several iterations in management, the community remains a focal point for Arctic research with the new Barrow Arctic Research Center and long term monitoring stations run by the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA), Department of Energy (DOE), and others. At sea, initial exploratory cruises in the late 19th and early 20th century yielded to more focused efforts in the 1970s; one of the major programs was NOAA and Minerals Management Service’s (MMS) Outer Continental Shelf Environmental Assessment Program (OCSEAP, 1975-1985), inspired by North Slope and offshore oil and gas potential. MMS’s environmental studies program continues to conduct research to support decisions with regard to offshore oil and gas leasing, at the level of some 50 ongoing projects in any year. The National Science Foundation (NSF) and the Office of Naval Research (ONR) have continued to fund interdisciplinary cruises in the area, notably the recent Shelf Basin Interaction program. NOAA and the Department of the Interior have supported joint research cruises with Russia through the BERPAC cruises of the 1980, and more recently the RUSALCA

program. Ice stations, ice mounted buoys, and numerous polar orbiting satellites contribute to monitoring in the region. University, federal and state agency, North Slope Borough, and oil and gas industry scientists have conducted, and continue to conduct, literally hundreds of research projects in the Beaufort and Chukchi seas and along the coasts. The local inhabitants, in some 15 villages along the coast, possess extensive traditional knowledge and continue to study the marine as well as terrestrial environment as an essential component of their subsistence activities.

2. The Challenges of Change in the Chukchi and Beaufort.

The intent of this brief and obviously very incomplete litany is simply to note that there is a large if unsystematic and mostly un-integrated body of available information about and knowledge of the area, as well as many continuing programs to study it. It is reasonable to ask, therefore – as this Workshop did – that if the current and past modus operandi is inadequate, what if anything has changed to suggest that a different approach to Arctic research and monitoring is needed; and if it is, what are the appropriate actions.

There would appear to be at least four major interacting forces that together imply that much more than a ‘business as usual’ approach to the US maritime Arctic is needed:

a. Climate Change. While this is a well-appreciated global issue, the changes in the Chukchi, Beaufort and surrounding regions appear to be larger, earlier, and more consequential than those in many other regions. The major physical manifestations are significantly reduced sea ice, and thawing permafrost. These in turn have very major impacts on other components of the environment, from rapid coastal erosion to loss of substrate for ice-dependent animals to changes in transportation patterns. The chain, or web, of impacts from these primary and readily visible manifestations is extensive. As just one example, while marine shipping for commerce, supply, exploration and tourism may be easier, subsistence activities are disrupted and endangered. Another striking change is the shift from a ‘benthic’ to ‘pelagic’ dominated ecosystem structure – already documented in the northern Bering Sea - as depicted in this figure, from the Workshop synthesis presentation by Prof. Russ Hopcroft¹. A new piece of information was

¹ Arctic Ocean Synthesis: Analysis of Climate Change Impacts in the Chukchi and Beaufort Seas with Strategies for Future Research, Hopcroft, Bluhm and Grading (Eds), available at www.aos.org; see also the NPRB-sponsored report on which the presentation was based, same title, December 2008, NPRB Project #503 available at www.nprb.org

presented at the workshop by Dr. John Walsh, who extended the climate projections of the UAF Scenarios Network for Alaska Planning project (www.snap.uaf.edu) to the offshore areas. The results indicate not only continued warming, especially in ice-free regions, but shifts in mean sea level pressure with resultant increases in winds from the south and accompanying increased inflow from the Bering Sea into the Arctic. The main point from both presenters is that although the anthropogenic and natural forces driving climate change in the Chukchi and Beaufort largely come from outside the area the impacts have already started, will be large, fundamental, and irreversible, and will require significant adaptation by virtually all trophic levels in the ecosystem, from microbes to man.

b. Vessel traffic. The Arctic Council’s Protection of the Arctic Marine Environment (PAME) working group is conducting an Arctic Marine Shipping Assessment, which should be released at this spring’s ministerial meeting. The expectation is that it will indicate the likelihood of significantly increased activity, even if the Northwest Passage and Northern Sea Route don’t become major shipping routes. One very significant component of increased offshore activity in the Chukchi and Beaufort? Seas will be continued oil and gas exploration, which picked up significantly following the 2008 lease sales. Eventually, pending resolution of court cases, it is expected that the oceanographic and seismic research of MMS and the industry will lead to exploratory drilling, and then production. In the interim the drive to develop the baseline data required for permitting brings many more research projects into the region. Exploratory drilling and production will obviously involve more permanent facilities, plus supply voyages and pipeline or other facility installations. These activities in turn, along with likely increased tourism, will require the development of enhanced safety infrastructure, from vessel tracking and management systems to Coast Guard patrols. The recently issued draft Arctic Fisheries Management Plan (FMP) states that “except for Pacific Salmon and Pacific Halibut, commercial fishing for those fish described in the FMP is prohibited in the Arctic Management Area under this FMP until sufficient information exists to authorize a sustainable fisheries management program”, so that other than survey cruises fishing is

not expected to contribute to increased ship traffic. Nonetheless, the overall increases in shipping and other offshore activity will interact with traditional subsistence activities, themselves often displaced or modified by changes in ice conditions.

c. National Policy. NSPD 66/HSPD 25, Arctic Region Policy, was signed by President Bush on January 9, 2009. It cites homeland security and defense, climate change and increased activity in the region, the work of the Arctic Council, and ‘growing awareness that the Arctic region is both fragile and rich in resources’ as rationale for the update of the 1994 PDD 26. One of the main drivers is the provision in the UN Convention on the Law of the Sea for sovereign national claims for an extended continental shelf (ECS). Other Arctic nations are exerting such claims under UNCLOS, and it is expected that the US will soon accede to the convention and do the same; exploratory cruises have already commenced. The policy document also notes the unresolved boundary between the US and Canada in the Beaufort Sea, which is in an area of expected significant oil and gas resources. Overall, the Policy discussed and directed implementation measures in national and homeland security, international governance, the ECS and boundary issues, international scientific cooperation, maritime transportation, economic issues including energy, and environmental protection and conservation. Essentially all the Executive Departments and many federal agencies now have additional charges that will require their attention to, and actions in, the Chukchi and Beaufort Seas.

d. Cumulative Impacts. All of the expected changes will inevitably have a significant impact on the way of life and culture of the local population. Although the oil and gas developments in and around Prudhoe Bay, and the Red Dog Mine, have inevitably influenced life in the region, they are somewhat separated geographically from most Alaska Native villages, and predominantly involve terrestrial and nearshore activity. The substantive changes expected in the coastal and offshore regions – both environmentally and human induced - are likely to be more directly intrusive, both in terms of infrastructure development and interference with culturally and socio-economically critical subsistence activities. The major concern is that the combination of activities may create unmitigable impacts on subsistence activities.

3. Responding to Change – Needs, Issues, and Initial Actions.

Following presentations at the workshop by several of the agencies and organizations with research and monitoring programs in the Arctic², panelists from the resource management community, industry, the communities and NGOs discussed their issues and data needs. Although expressed in many ways, there was remarkable consistency in core requirements. First and foremost is the need for a sound baseline of environmental and ecological conditions on which to base decisions and anticipate the impacts likely to be caused by the major forces for change. Although as noted above there is a long history of research and a large body of data and information, coverage is incomplete and much of what is available hasn’t been synthesized or integrated. Examples of major gaps that

² Their viewgraphs are on the AOOS web site. Current projects will soon be available through the Alaska Marine Information System, jointly developed by AOOS and NPRB, and available soon on their websites.

were cited include accurate bathymetry, population abundance and dynamics of key species and in particular marine mammals, background noise levels, and contaminants.

The second major need is better understanding of the key interactions, both natural as in the above diagram, and human related, with a key issue being bowhead whale reaction to the noise and installations associated with oil and gas exploration and other marine activity. Third is better (higher resolution, more timely and frequent) reporting and forecasts on conditions which impact human activity, be it subsistence related, industrial, or research itself. Ice and weather are at the top of the list, followed closely by information on the activities themselves – who is doing what and where, both for safety and to avoid conflict. The basic contention is that those who live and work in the region now need and deserve at least the same level of ‘service’ as routinely provided in more heavily populated areas, and in many cases require even more detailed information because of the inherent dangers of the environment. From the Alaska Native perspective, change has already been great enough that traditional knowledge, while essential, is no longer sufficient for safety and successful subsistence, and they need information on a very local, ‘human’ scale.

While it’s relatively easy to outline needs at this very general level, it’s equally difficult to prioritize specific requirements – e.g., which time series to collect, which trophic levels to focus on, which ‘hot spots’ to study in detail, which models to develop – and then to translate such specifics into actual programs. Such activities are of course conducted by each of the research and monitoring sponsors as part of their own planning and budgeting processes. The problem is always that the interests, mandates, and procedures of the sponsors and their performers don’t necessarily match up well, and the sum of the effort will thus continue to be incomplete in terms of the topical, temporal, and spatial coverage that a systematic, top-down, long term approach to understanding these two Large Marine Ecosystems as a ‘system’ would entail. Workshops such as the present one provide impetus toward coordination and suggestions for action plans, but they are periodic episodic? and infrequent at best and sponsors are not empowered to implement many if any of the well meaning recommendations they develop.

In this case however, there are a couple of specific actions in support of better collaboration that were being planned before the workshop and received additional guidance during the action planning session. The most significant is the development and evolution of the Alaska Marine Information System (AMIS) sponsored by the Alaska Ocean Observing System (AOOS) with additional support from NPRB. In addition to providing a significant amount of new information of use to managers and users on AMIS³, AOOS is collaborating with the North Slope Science Initiative (NSSI) to develop a common project tracking data base that should significantly help sponsors and researchers better coordinate their plans and efforts. NSSI’s data base is being managed by the Geographical Information Network for Alaska (GINA), where it is combined with other mapping tools and satellite data capture and display. AMIS and GINA are both

³ AMIS is still in development, but you can learn more about it and give it a trial at ak.aos.org/amis/demo. You are urged to try it and comment.

managed and operated at the University of Alaska Fairbanks, and the two programs are increasing their collaboration to better support both terrestrial and marine users.

Other aspects of information sharing and data management that were discussed included the need for a ready source of information on upcoming meetings and workshops, ship schedules and availability (this is always a hard problem to solve), and coordination and timeliness of requests for information from or approval to work in or near Arctic communities to minimize the burdens on the people and ensure that the protocols of the native organizations are followed. The desirability of improving access to industry data and reports was raised frequently, and it was suggested that the Alaska Oil and Gas Association (AOGA) work with its 16 member organizations to serve as an interface to other users. The attached Action Plan Draft includes additional ideas.

Two additional relatively new coordination mechanisms were mentioned, although not stressed, at the workshop. The first is the NOAA's Integrated Service Plan, developed by its Alaska Regional Collaboration Team (ARCTic). NOAA's new emphasis on regional coordination and planning holds great promise for providing more integrated, timely, and precise information in support of the third major need mentioned above, as well as enhanced contributions to the baseline. Similarly, USGS now has an Alaska Regional Science Officer to help integrate and coordinate the efforts of its biology, geology, geography and water programs in its Alaska Integrated Science Center and other DOI research units.

4. Longer term Actions and Plans: Baselines, Syntheses, Processes, and Models.

If indeed, as workshop participants agreed, a sound baseline is essential to support the decisions that are so critical to economic development and simultaneous preservation of the subsistence based lifestyle of the area's residents, then the process must start with a synthesis of available information. There have been three recent efforts to develop such a synthesis. The first, presented publicly for the first time at the Workshop, is the "Arctic Ocean Synthesis: Analysis of Climate Change Impacts in the Chukchi and Beaufort Seas with Strategies for Future Research", Hopcroft, Bluhm and Gradinger (Eds), December 2008, NPRB Project #503, discussed above. This report, based on workshops among principally academic researchers in 2006, describes the physical and chemical oceanography of the region and then focuses upon ecology, describing what is and isn't known about various trophic levels from microbes to marine mammals. It is silent on geology, contaminants, acoustics, and humans. The viewgraphs from Prof. Hopcroft's presentation outline the major conclusions -- the increasing impact of Pacific waters and species, the shift of the ecosystem structure from benthic to pelagic dominated, threats to taxa that range from loss of sea ice to predator-prey mismatches and potentially lethal temperatures -- and major deficiencies in our baseline knowledge, notably the dearth of information about protists, and the lack of adequate knowledge despite massive effort about marine mammal population sizes and major aspects of their population dynamics.

The second major synthesis is Chapter 3, Existing Environment, of the MMS Draft Environmental Impact Statement for the Beaufort and Chukchi Sea Planning Areas Oil

and Gas Lease Sales 209, 212, 217 and 221 (OCS EIA/EA MMS 2008-0055 of November 2008). Appendix C, Petroleum Geology of Arctic Alaska Offshore, contains additional baseline information. While the MMS Planning Areas are not contiguous with the Large Marine Ecosystem boundaries, and MMS is concerned primarily with Federal waters thus leaving a three-mile nearshore gap, this draft report extends the synthesis to climate and meteorology, water quality, geology, sound, terrestrial mammals, and the social systems of the North Slope, as well as oceanography and marine ecology.

The third is the North Pacific Fisheries Management Council's "Public Review Draft Environmental Assessment/Regulatory Impact Review/Initial Regulatory Flexibility Analysis for the Arctic Fishery Management Plan and Amendment 29 to the Fishery Management Plan for Bering Sea/Aleutian Islands King and Tanner Crabs" of January 2009. In support of the alternatives considered by the Council, this draft provides background information on the ecosystems and fish habitat as well as synthesized information on marine mammals and birds as well as fish.

Because all three of these documents are so new, and because both the MMS EIS and the NPFMC EA are drafts awaiting public comment and revision, no attempt has been made to 'synthesize the syntheses', and make an overall evaluation of the gaps in the information they contain. Further, as noted by Hopcroft, there are large volumes of additional historical data that have not yet been mined. There is little doubt however that some of his conclusions and recommendations – e.g. the need for long time series, year round and in particular winter data, filling the trophic and process gaps briefly mentioned above, and identifying and filling important geographic gaps (e.g. Herald Valley, the Beaufort Sea Slope, Long Strait) – would be sustained even after the three reports have been integrated and additional available data incorporated in the baseline assessment. While there will always be debate on how much is enough, the workshop participants were quite unanimous in their contention that what we know is far from adequate for sound decision making.

What might be a way forward to finally develop a baseline that would meet the needs of the multiple stakeholders for the Chukchi and Beaufort Seas? One promising opportunity is offered by the long-awaited arrival of the NSF-funded Alaska Region Research Vessel (ARRV) to be built under the management of, and operated by UAF. Having already passed its final review, if funds become available this year as expected, the ship could be commissioned and ready to operate in 3-4 years. It is ice strengthened although not an ice breaker, and will be fully outfitted for the whole range of oceanographic research. With a modicum of assistance from US Coast Guard icebreakers, a carefully designed suite of in-situ sensors, and the assumption that ice conditions will remain about as they have been for the last few years, it would appear that a dedicated effort focused around ARRV cruises for approximately 4-5 years could provide enough temporal and spatial coverage to both fill in the gaps and significantly extend our knowledge.

What would it take to make this happen? First of course, NSF must be convinced that in spite of the normal procedure for scheduling the UNOLS fleet by responding to proposals...in which case the ARRV could well end up virtually anywhere...it is in the

interests of science as well as the nation to formulate a dedicated strategic long term cruise plan that concentrates on the US Arctic for the ARRV's first few years of operation. This is not at all illogical given the intent of the ship, and the fact that it could support several Arctic Observing Network projects (e.g. Beaufort Gyre) and the Bering Sea initiatives as well as adequately covering the Chukchi and Beaufort. Because the ship will not be available for several years, there is adequate time to obtain the necessary funding commitments from federal agencies, 'synthesize the syntheses' and augment them with newly mined and developed data, and then involve communities, agencies, industries and academic researchers in focused workshops to specify in detail the gaps and develop cruise plans as well as recommendations for moorings, ice and bottom mounted sensors, aircraft and UAV flights, etc to accompany the ships. In the interim, ongoing research and monitoring such as described at the workshop (as well as better 'services' through NOAA's ARCTic) could be better coordinated by the sort of science steering committee and working group structure that would be required to oversee the synthesis development and develop the ARRV 'campaign plan'. Certainly this approach is feasible; at issue is whether the community believes it is justified by the anticipated results and is willing to cooperate adequately to dedicate funds and staff to make it happen.

An enhanced baseline will be most useful if it is accompanied by the sort of process studies and modeling that enable projections. John Walsh's presentation provided a glimpse at what can be done, now, in the area of climate related parameters; Henry Huntington provided a much more sobering picture of our inability to deal with the socioeconomic and human dimension aspects of change. While there are a number of fundamental mechanistic questions that can best be answered by dedicated research in the Chukchi and Beaufort or neighboring regions (as just one example, the benthic-pelagic switch), many of the important processes are global or pan-Arctic in nature, so that local and regional efforts should be 'nested' within the larger body of ongoing global and Arctic-wide programs. The workshop did not address this issue, albeit the connections are implicit in that the sponsor AOOS is one of 11 regional programs within the larger US IOOS program which itself is a component of GOOS and IEOS which themselves feed into GEOSS (see <http://ioos.noaa.gov/partners/global.html>). There is a similarly dizzying string of acronyms for global climate studies, see for example <http://wcrp.wmo.int/wcrp-index.html>. On the Arctic level the main US climate research program is SEARCH, which drives AON and couples into European and international efforts such as ISAC, DAMOCLES and S4D as well as neighboring programs in Canada such as CASES and C3O. Similarly, there are a host of satellite programs of NASA, NOAA, USGS and their international counterparts which come together in GEOSS but have particular relevance to the US Arctic because of the large number of passes of polar orbiting satellites that cover the region. An additional effort of particular interest that is spinning up is the Arctic System Model⁴. Further, a SCICEX Phase II science plan is in review, and the periodic Navy ice camps offer excellent opportunities for process studies.

The essential point is that regional and local programs need to be coupled in some fashion to these larger efforts, if for no other reason than that they have major

⁴ see http://research.iarc.uaf.edu/presentations/ASM_08/ASM_Science_Plan_draft_02Dec08.doc

implications for funding and other resources, including the time and attention of investigators. At issue of course is how to keep track of the myriad programs at the agency, national and international level to take advantage of their contributions, and leverage them toward attention to or coverage of the Chukchi and Beaufort.

5. Organization and Process.

Three verbs heard frequently at the Workshop, in presentations as well as at the action planning session, were ‘collaborate, cooperate, and communicate’. Certainly the recommendations in the action plan draft and this report need leadership and vision to make them happen. What is required to develop a baseline and an accompanying overall plan is a ‘community’ effort, where the term community includes all the stakeholders from villages to federal agencies and industry. The tried and true process for planning systematic, coordinated efforts like those envisaged is to establish an oversight or governance committee where via MOAs the interested parties commit to contribute and monitor progress and share data, plus an overall Scientific Steering Committee to guide the research and monitoring planning, with specific details and plans developed by a series of Working Groups.

Lacking such a structure, we can all meet annually at the Alaska Marine Science Symposium to exchange information, attend topical workshops as they appear to one or more of the agencies to be important to their interests, and hope that some entity with coordination and facilitation as part of its mission helps with collaboration. What’s at stake? In addition to the health of the ecosystem, the Chukchi and Beaufort are critical to the culture and subsistence lifestyle of the local Alaska Native population, the nation’s energy future, and the opportunity to significantly extend the nation’s territory and sovereign rights. It seems to many who attended the workshop that it’s well worth the effort to be serious about carrying out the charge of the workshop to develop ‘a more comprehensive monitoring and assessment plan, through which each participating organization can focus on projects to meet its particular goals while contributing to a larger data sharing and integration effort’.

My personal view is that AOOS should be tasked with coordinating this initiative. AOOS was conceived as an umbrella regional organization to coordinate ocean observing efforts in Alaska’s three LMEs: the Gulf of Alaska, the Bering Sea, and the Arctic (combining the Chukchi and Beaufort LMEs for this purpose). Its Governance Committee has representatives from most of the interested parties, and its national program, IOOS, is very likely to receive authorization in Federal statute this session. AOOS has a significant demonstration project in Prince William Sound, enhances collaboration and data sharing through its web site and AMIS, and supports a number of research and monitoring projects (such as the Bering Sea Integrated Ecosystem Research Program), often in conjunction with the NPRB. Although AOOS currently has limited resources, it may well be the one organization – as the Workshop demonstrated – that has the reach and the structure needed to pull the parties together. The other organization with a broad reach, and significant resources, is the North Pacific Research Board. Coordinating research activities could fall within its scope, although thus far, the NPRB board has not

embraced long-term coordination and facilitation activities as part of its mission. A final recommendation of this report – implicit if not explicit in the output of action planning session - is that the AOOS and NPRB boards consider taking a larger role in leading a coordinated planning effort for the Chukchi and Beaufort Seas as suggested here and during the Workshop.

DRAFT

Arctic Research and Monitoring

Draft Action Plan

January 23, 2009

Note: The concepts included in this draft plan were developed in the discussion segment of the Arctic Research and Monitoring Workshop hosted by the Alaska Ocean Observing System and the North Pacific Research Board in Anchorage January 23, 2009. These ideas were not endorsed by the group as a whole, but rather, are included in this document to promote discussion and further dialogue on how to increase coordination and collaboration among the community of stakeholders interested in Arctic research and monitoring. The presentation segments of the workshop were attended by approximately 140 people. About 75 people attended the action discussion segment.

Data management

- Project Tracking Database
 - AMIS & NSSI efforts are merging
 - Circulate format, get additional input
 - How to organize – what key words, trophic levels, GIS based?
 - Make key words simple. - Consider adding field of “end user” and field for data center repository.
 - Look to NASA GCM global dictionary for key words.
 - How to keep up to date?
 - Have annual call for projects to submit into AMIS.
 - Use 2 entry points: distributed (seamlessly tie into large agency project databases) and individual submission.
 - Great Lakes International Commission – good model. Email reply when you submit.
 - Metadata – any issues?
 - Data
 - Sharing among parties – MOAs; high level agreement; what types of data, scales, timelines?
 - Have major AK data committees meet to ensure coordination, collaboration, interoperability
 - Data mining \$\$ is critical
 - Need for statewide data archive?
 - Most end users want information products, and those that are species specific.

Logistics

- Sharing ship time, cruises
- Who take lead?
 - Need plan for funding, maintenance
- Website to post opportunities
 - yes, good outreach tool to communities
- Ice breakers

- lag time for requesting ship time; no cruise lists due to security; check AICC website (per Carin); ice flow web (Coast Guard & UNOLS)
- Industry vessels
 - need early coordination. Key is personal contacts/relationships.
 - Check out ARMAP – NSF website – maintained by CH2M Hill – Polar Sea
 - NOAA ship trackers
- Share UAS, submersible, gliders, other?
 - How to influence design of moorings to add additional sensors
- Use ArcticInfo to advertise opportunities; MARMAM (?) other list servs? ArcticNet (Canada); ARCUS maintained Directory of Arctic Researchers
- Coordinate community outreach activities? Lead?
- Website with community contacts/Native organizations.
- Post pertinent research protocols. Hire regional liaisons.
- Use EPA's IGAP program – they look for new tasks; training. Not all tribes have IGAP
- Highlight best practices
- Alaska Beluga Whale Commission successful: continuity, accountability, can make decisions & focus priorities
- How to make contact with tribe, city, and Native corporation?
- Information transfer
- Meeting schedules on Arctic issues to increase cross-communication & overall project awareness in communities
- Consider changing AMSS week to avoid conflict with Arctic Frontiers week
- MMS considering incorporating Information Transfer Meetings (ITMs) to merge with AMSS
- What about Arctic Observing Network and other Arctic meetings?
- How to keep state of information up to date? Annual meeting? How to add international component?

Follow-up road map

- Workshop report
 - Synthesis summary
 - Follow-up action items
 - Additional review steps?
- Next steps
 - MOAs?
 - Draft “umbrella” Arctic strategy
 - Committee to keep on planning strategies to address gaps? Who take lead?
 - Follow-up workshop(s)
 - How to incorporate “State of Arctic” and “State of Sea Ice” initiatives
 - Advocate for requirement of publication to have a “data accession number”.

Synthesis & gap analysis

- Develop an overall Arctic research and monitoring plan
 - Robert Suydam (North Slope Borough) – this could be one of the best things to happen for the region
 - Use Hopcroft report as start. Include gray literature reports at ARLIS.
 - Brendan Kelly (NSF) – start w/SEARCH plan & others

- Define user needs & integrative structure
- Use final, peer reviewed publication data.
- How to incorporate current & planned projects?
- What about historical data?
- Can we define set of common information goals? Can we agree on what is a gap?
- Define key geographic areas (if any); key processes to be investigated based on needs/wants; key temporal coverage
- Data gaps are in the eye of the beholder, can be based on policy needs, regulation & permit needs, overall scientific understanding
- Key themes that arose from presentations
 - Sea ice, weather, acoustics (noise), bathymetry, species of primary interest
- Geographic gaps
 - Beaufort & Chukchi – repeat OCSEAP cross shelf transects, would give 30 year comparison
 - Nearshore bathymetry, shore to 20 miles out
- Temporal gaps
 - winter & year round observations
- Trophic level gaps
 - Water & air quality ground & across Beaufort & Chukchi seas
 - AON marine – mainly physical, need more bio & chemical sensors; add acoustic recorders
 - currents under ice/broken ice and throughout water column
 - tide data
 - ocean acidification
- Trophic level gaps
 - Function & change of social-ecological systems
 - Human dimension studies
 - Animal adaptation: molecular, chemical/physical
 - Overwintering mechanisms – little known
 - How do processes scale with change in temperature?
 - Ecological adaptations: we focus on potential declines, but many species will adapt, but how?
 - Population level – need to know food, migration

ARCTIC RESEARCH AND MONITORING WORKSHOP

**Friday, January 23, 2009, Anchorage, Hotel Captain Cook Fore Deck
Ballroom**

Purpose

The goal of this workshop is to share information and promote collaboration among the many entities with increasing activities in marine research and monitoring in the region, including the oil and gas industry, local, state, and federal agencies, and non-governmental and academic organizations. The workshop will include panel discussions of data user and provider issues and needs in the region. This workshop is an initial step toward a longer term development of a more comprehensive monitoring and assessment plan, through which each participating organization can focus on projects to meet its particular goals while contributing to a larger data sharing and integration effort.

Desired Outcomes

- Development of a searchable database of current Arctic research projects
- A geographic depiction of where projects are occurring
- Synthesis of Arctic syntheses
- Preliminary Identification of gaps and needs in Arctic research and monitoring
- Strategies for further coordination and collaboration
- Workshop report that will go out for additional review and input and will then be submitted for consideration by a number of entities: NSSI, NPRB, AOOS, etc.

8-8:05 am Welcome, introduction to workshop, purpose, desired outcomes – Molly McCammon

8:05-10:15 am Arctic research programmatic summaries: Who's doing what where

Broad mission programs

Alaska Ocean Observing System – Molly McCammon (5 min)

North Pacific Research Board – Francis Wiese (5 min)

US Arctic Research Commission – Michele Longo Eder (5 min)

North Slope Science Initiative – John Payne (5 min)

State and local agencies

Alaska Department of Fish & Game – Lori Quakenbush (10 min)

North Slope Borough – Cheryl Rosa (10 min)

Alaska Department of Environmental Conservation – Doug Dasher (5 min)

Federal agencies

Minerals Management Service – Dee Williams (15 min)
USGS – Mark Shasby (10 min)
US Fish and Wildlife Service – Doug Burn (10 min)
NOAA – Amy Holman (10 min)
National Science Foundation – Alison York, ARCUS (10 min)
Oil & Gas Industry
BP – Diane Sanzone (10 min)
Conoco-Phillips – Caryn Rea (10 min)
Shell – Michael Macrander (10 min)

10:15–10:30 am Break

10:30 am – 12:00 Arctic data user and provider issues & needs. 5 min presentations, then discussion. Each panel approx 30 min. Facilitated by Henry Huntington.

Resource manager panel:

USFWS: Doug Burn
NOAA: Bill Wilson, NPFMC
ADF&G: Lori Quakenbush
ADEC: Doug Dasher
US Coast Guard: CDR Shane Montoya

Industry panel:

Oil and gas: Sami Glascott, AOGA
Shipping: Bruce Harland, Crowley
Commercial fisheries: TBD
Large mines: (Helvi Sandvik invited)

NGO/Community/subsistence panel:

North Slope Borough: Robert Suydam
Barrow subsistence user: Billy Adams
Eskimo Walrus Commission: Vera Metcalf
The Nature Conservancy: Steve MacLean

12 – 1:00 pm Lunch provided

1:00 – 2:30 pm Synthesis presentations analysis of what’s been done (past synthesis reports, existing resources), what folks are proposing, preliminary identification of big gaps. Facilitated by Dr. Craig Dorman
Dr. Russ Hopcroft (marine ecosystem) – 30 min
Dr. John Walsh (climate, weather) – 15 min
Dr. Henry Huntington (LTK, socio-economic, human dimension) – 15 min
Facilitated discussion – 30 min

2:30 – 3 pm Adjourn to Quarter Deck (10th floor, Tower 1) for break and remainder of afternoon

3-5 pm Action group: Where do go from here; what are big gaps & needs.
Develop action plan. Facilitated by Francis Wiese and Molly McCammon

ARCTIC RESEARCH AND MONITORING WORKSHOP
Friday, January 23, 2009, Anchorage, Hotel Captain Cook Fore Deck Ballroom

Participant List

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Summary of Proposed Funding 4/6/09 12:18	5 Year	2008 APPROVED BUDGET	2008 TOTAL ACTUAL (9-month year)	2008 FUNDS REMAINING (SHORTFALL)	2009 YEAR 2
	APPROVED BUDGET	BUDGET NINE MONTHS			
1. ARCTIC COMMUNITY SCIENCE PLANNING					
1.1 SEARCH Coordination	1,652,935	283,534	206,572	76,963	322,656
1.2 Arctic Data Coordination	26,932	28,167	10,196	17,971	20,237
1.3 State of the Arctic	-	-	-	-	273,245
Subtotal Direct Costs	1,679,867	311,701	216,768	94,933	616,137
Indirect Costs	638,349	118,446	82,398	36,048	234,132
	2,318,216	430,147	299,166	130,981	850,269
2. NSF ARCTIC SCIENCES SECTION COORDINATION					
2.1 ARCSS Program Coordination					
2.1.1 ARCSS Coordination	1,456,343	261,240	143,922	117,318	157,387
2.2 Arctic Natural Sciences Program Coordination					
2.2.1 Bering Sea Research Coordination	208,419	48,380	12,801	35,579	58,257
2.3 Arctic Social Sciences Program Coordination					
2.3.1 Arctic Social Sciences Coordination	25,733	-	-	-	-
2.4 Arctic Section Science Materials					
2.4.1 Arctic Section Science Materials	54,346	2,515	-	2,515	7,861
Subtotal Direct Costs	1,744,841	312,136	156,723	155,413	223,505
Indirect Costs	621,765	77,337	21,117	56,219	82,668
	2,366,606	389,472	177,840	211,632	306,173
3. ARCTIC SCIENCE EDUCATION					
3.1 Arctic Science Education Activities	171,737	25,959	24,763	1,196	19,622
3.2 Arctic Visiting Speakers	167,276	13,301	5,454	7,847	25,309
Subtotal Direct Costs	339,013	39,261	30,217	9,044	44,932
Indirect Costs	128,825	14,919	11,482	3,437	17,075
	467,838	54,180	41,699	12,480	62,006
4. INFORMATION AND OUTREACH					
4.1 Witness the Arctic Newsletters	414,600	52,869	36,861	16,008	83,127
4.2 Website/ Internet Resources	612,806	101,419	108,974	(7,555)	131,221
4.3 ArcticInfo Listserver	172,448	8,509	14,334	(5,825)	24,014
4.4 Directory of Arctic Researchers	150,943	3,958	1,002	2,956	13,873
4.5 Internet Media Archive	264,573	5,241	7,087	(1,846)	37,510
4.6 Arctic Community Outreach	848,239	222,005	235,776	(13,771)	91,484
Subtotal Direct Costs	2,463,609	394,001	404,034	(10,033)	381,228
Indirect Costs	936,171	149,720	153,533	(3,813)	144,866
	3,399,780	543,721	557,567	(13,845)	526,094
5. CORE SUPPORT					
5.1 Core Support	1,286,073	94,953	231,553	(136,599)	247,387
Subtotal Direct Costs	1,286,073	94,953	231,553	(136,599)	247,387
Indirect Costs	480,804	36,082	87,990	(51,908)	94,007
	1,766,877	131,036	319,543	(188,507)	341,394
Total Direct Costs	7,513,403	1,151,982	1,039,408	112,574	1,513,192
Total Indirect Costs	2,805,915	396,480	356,406	40,074	572,750
TOTAL	10,319,318	1,548,462	1,395,815	152,648	2,085,941

ATTACHMENT A

Arctic Research Consortium of the United States, Inc.					
Budget Explanation	5 Year	2008	2008	2008	2009
	APPROVED BUDGET	APPROVED BUDGET	(9-month year)	month year)	YEAR 2
		NINE MONTHS	TOTAL	FUNDS	
			ACTUAL	REMAINING (Shortfall)	
I. ARCTIC COMMUNITY SCIENCE PLANNING					
1.1 SEARCH Coordination					
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	859,692	101,901	79,569	22,332	95,144
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic/foreign)	74,263	27,744	22,219	5,525	31,200
Participant Support Costs	447,500	124,489	54,964	69,525	139,912
Materials and Supplies	8,800	1,000	161	839	2,000
Publications/Dissemination	37,480	2,500	3,153	(653)	7,400
Consulting	2,000	5,750	3,050	2,700	5,000
Computer Services	17,250	1,000	2,578	(1,578)	4,000
Subawards	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	205,950	19,150	40,878	(21,728)	38,000
Total direct costs	1,652,935	283,534	206,572	76,963	322,656
Total indirect costs	628,115	107,743	78,524	29,219	122,609
	2,281,050	391,277	285,095	106,182	445,265
1.2 Arctic Data Coordination					
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	15,005	16,277	5,189	11,088	7,107
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	3,550	-	3,007	(3,007)	2,600
Participant Support Costs	5,325	2,490	-	2,490	-
Materials and Supplies	150	150	-	150	80
Publications/Dissemination	-	250	75	175	450
Consulting	-	8,000	1,500	6,500	10,000
Computer Services	-	-	-	-	-
Subawards	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	2,902	1,000	425	575	-
Total direct costs	26,932	28,167	10,196	17,971	20,237
Total indirect costs	10,234	10,703	3,874	6,829	7,690
	37,166	38,870	14,070	24,799	27,927
1.3 State of the Arctic					
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	-	-	-	-	202,545
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	-	-	-	-	5,200
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	-	36,000
Materials and Supplies	-	-	-	-	8,000
Publications/Dissemination	-	-	-	-	5,500
Consulting	-	-	-	-	15,000
Computer Services	-	-	-	-	5,000
Subawards	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	-	-	-	-	(4,000)
Total direct costs	-	-	-	-	273,245
Total indirect costs	-	-	-	-	103,833
TOTAL FOR SOA	-	-	-	-	377,077
Subtotal Direct Community Science Planning	1,679,867	311,701	216,768	94,933	616,137
Subtotal Indirect	638,349	118,446	82,398	36,048	234,132
Total Community Science Planning	2,318,216	430,147	299,166	130,981	850,269

Arctic Research Consortium of the United States, Inc.						
Budget Explanation	5 Year	2008	2008	2008	(9	2009
	APPROVED BUDGET	APPROVED BUDGET	(9-month year)	month year)		YEAR 2
			TOTAL	FUNDS		
2. NSF ARCTIC SCIENCES SECTION COORDINATION						
2.1 ARCSS PROGRAM COORDINATION						
2.1.1 ARCSS Coordination						
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	870,626	106,166	13,245	92,921		62,004
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-		-
Travel (domestic)	30,625	9,650	3,851	5,799		5,200
Participant Support Costs	185,675	14,939	6,734	8,205		67,965
Materials and Supplies	870	120	69	51		200
Publications/Dissemination	1,482	220	10	210		160
Consulting	201,200	11,000	-	11,000		1,200
Computer Services	17,250	5,500	5,156	344		3,000
Subawards	108,615	108,615	101,148	7,467		5,958
Other Direct Costs	40,000	5,030	13,709	(8,679)		11,700
Total direct costs	1,456,343	261,240	143,922	117,318		157,387
Total indirect costs	512,137	57,997	16,254	41,743		57,543
	1,968,480	319,237	160,176	159,061		214,930
2.2 ARCTIC NATURAL SCIENCES PROGRAM COORDINATION						
2.2.1 Bering Sea Research Coordination						
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	112,198	12,273	2,632	9,641		17,011
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-		-
Travel (domestic)	9,025	2,413	989	1,424		2,600
Participant Support Costs	75,850	22,408	8,429	13,979		22,386
Materials and Supplies	420	180	69	111		160
Publications/Dissemination	7,526	7,000	10	6,990		15,000
Consulting	-	1,000	-	1,000		-
Computer Services	-	-	-	-		1,000
Subawards	-	-	-	-		-
Other Direct Costs	3,400	3,107	672	2,435		100
Total direct costs	208,419	48,380	12,801	35,579		58,257
Total indirect costs	79,199	18,385	4,864	13,520		22,138
	287,618	66,765	17,665	49,100		80,395
2.3 ARCTIC SOCIAL SCIENCES PROGRAM COORDINATION						
2.3.1 Arctic Social Sciences Coordination						
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	25,733	-	-	-		-
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-		-
Travel (domestic)	-	-	-	-		-
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	-		-
Materials and Supplies	-	-	-	-		-
Publications/Dissemination	-	-	-	-		-
Consulting	-	-	-	-		-
Computer Services	-	-	-	-		-
Subawards	-	-	-	-		-
Other Direct Costs	-	-	-	-		-
Total direct costs	25,733	-	-	-		-
Total indirect costs	9,779	-	-	-		-
	35,512	-	-	-		-

Arctic Research Consortium of the United States, Inc.					
Budget Explanation	5 Year	2008	2008	2008	2009
	APPROVED BUDGET	APPROVED BUDGET	(9-month year) TOTAL	(9 month year) FUNDS	YEAR 2
2.4 ARCTIC SECTION SCIENCE MATERIALS					
2.4.1 Arctic Section Science Materials					
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	54,046	2,215	-	2,215	7,461
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	-	-
Materials and Supplies	-	-	-	-	-
Publications/Dissemination	-	300	-	300	400
Consulting	-	-	-	-	-
Computer Services	-	-	-	-	-
Subawards	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	300	-	-	-	-
Total direct costs	54,346	2,515	-	2,515	7,861
Total indirect costs	20,651	956	-	956	2,987
	74,997	3,470	-	3,470	10,848
Subtotal Direct Costs Arctic Sciences Section	1,744,841	312,136	156,723	155,413	223,505
Subtotal Indirect Costs	621,765	77,337	21,117	56,219	82,668
Total Arctic Sciences Section	2,366,606	389,472	177,840	211,632	306,173
3. ARCTIC SCIENCE EDUCATION					
3.1 Arctic Science Education Activities					
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	106,068	10,503	8,790	1,713	12,879
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	9,025	2,413	6,763	(4,351)	-
Participant Support Costs	30,625	11,204	5,556	5,648	2,798
Materials and Supplies	1,250	250	-	250	150
Publications/Dissemination	269	90	953	(863)	20
Consulting	-	-	-	-	-
Computer Services	15,500	1,000	-	1,000	3,375
Subawards	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	9,000	500	2,701	(2,201)	400
Total direct costs	171,737	25,959	24,763	1,196	19,622
Total indirect cost	65,260	9,865	9,410	455	7,456
	236,997	35,824	34,173	1,651	27,079
3.2 Arctic Visiting Speakers					
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	70,926	5,032	2,033	2,999	13,109
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	96,350	8,269	2,502	5,767	12,200
Materials and Supplies	-	-	-	-	-
Publications/Dissemination	-	-	127	(127)	-
Consulting	-	-	-	-	-
Computer Services	-	-	-	-	-
Subawards	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	-	-	792	(792)	-
Total direct costs	167,276	13,301	5,454	7,847	25,309
Total indirect costs	63,565	5,055	2,073	2,982	9,618
	230,841	18,356	7,527	10,829	34,928
Subtotal Direct Costs Arctic Science Education	339,013	39,261	30,217	9,044	44,932
Subtotal Indirect Costs	128,825	14,919	11,482	3,437	17,075
Total Arctic Science Education	467,838	54,180	41,699	12,480	62,006

Arctic Research Consortium of the United States, Inc.					
Budget Explanation	5 Year	2008	2008	2008	2009
	APPROVED BUDGET	APPROVED BUDGET	(9-month year) TOTAL	(9 month year) FUNDS	
4. INFORMATION AND OUTREACH					
4.1 Witness the Arctic Newsletters					
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	296,100	20,169	21,506	(1,337)	28,027
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	-	-
Materials and Supplies	-	100	-	100	100
Publications/Dissemination	-	23,600	30	23,570	40,000
Consulting	-	9,000	15,325	(6,325)	15,000
Computer Services	-	-	-	-	-
Subawards	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	118,500	-	-	-	-
Total direct costs	414,600	52,869	36,861	16,008	83,127
Total indirect costs	157,548	20,090	14,007	6,083	31,588
	572,148	72,958	50,868	22,090	114,715
4.2 ARCUS Internet Resources					
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	550,031	100,419	108,889	(8,470)	116,421
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	30,775	-	85	(85)	7,800
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	-	-
Materials and Supplies	-	-	-	-	-
Publications/Dissemination	-	-	-	-	-
Consulting	-	1,000	-	1,000	7,000
Computer Services	-	-	-	-	-
Subawards	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	32,000	-	-	-	-
Total direct costs	612,806	101,419	108,974	(7,555)	131,221
Total indirect costs	232,866	38,539	41,410	(2,871)	49,864
	845,672	139,958	150,384	(10,426)	181,085
4.3 ArcticInfo Listserver					
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	172,448	8,509	14,334	(5,825)	24,014
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	-	-
Materials and Supplies	-	-	-	-	-
Publications/Dissemination	-	-	-	-	-
Consulting	-	-	-	-	-
Computer Services	-	-	-	-	-
Subawards	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	-	-	-	-	-
Total direct costs	172,448	8,509	14,334	(5,825)	24,014
Total indirect costs	65,530	3,233	5,447	(2,214)	9,125
	237,978	11,742	19,781	(8,039)	33,139
4.4 Directory of Arctic Researchers					
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	142,693	3,958	1,002	2,956	13,873
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	7,250	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	-	-
Materials and Supplies	-	-	-	-	-
Publications/Dissemination	-	-	-	-	-
Consulting	-	-	-	-	-
Computer Services	-	-	-	-	-
Subawards	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	1,000	-	-	-	-
Total direct costs	150,943	3,958	1,002	2,956	13,873
Total indirect costs	57,358	1,504	381	1,123	5,272
	208,301	5,463	1,383	4,080	19,145

Form 1030 Summary

SUMMARY OF PROPOSED FUNDING			5-year	5-Year	2008	2008	2009
Form 1030 Category		Budget	Approved	Total	Funds	Remaining	Year 2
			For NINE Months	Actual	(Shortfall)		Budget
				(9 month year)			
Salaries							
President	A1	-					-
Executive director	A1	545,118	55,877	45,805	10,072		84,339
Other professionals	B2	2,281,849	275,900	231,758	44,142		450,382
Student	B3	71,700	16,261	34,344	(18,083)		30,215
Clerical	B5	477,505	12,934	14,084	(1,150)		42,406
Total salaries		3,376,172	360,973	325,992	34,981		607,341
Fringe Benefits							
Total salaries and fringe benefits	C	1,282,945	137,170	130,016	7,154		230,790
		4,659,117	498,142	456,008	42,134		838,132
Permanent Equipment							
	D	20,800	-	20,800	(20,800)		-
Travel (domestic)							
	E1	309,800	65,138	70,614	(5,477)		67,600
Travel (foreign)							
	E2	24,188	14,475	-	14,475		7,800
Total staff travel	E	333,988	79,613	70,614	8,999		75,400
Participant Support Costs							
Stipends	F1	42,200	800	400	400		13,400
Travel	F2	521,500	100,650	61,607	39,043		135,300
Subsistence	F3	494,375	127,165	60,483	66,682		132,561
Total participant costs		1,058,075	228,615	122,490	106,125		281,261
Other Direct Costs							
Materials and supplies	G1	233,890	6,810	21,951	(15,141)		56,290
Publication cost/ docum/dissem	G2	238,566	52,860	18,968	33,892		97,950
Consultant services	G3	305,700	51,250	40,575	10,675		60,200
Computer services	G4	66,875	31,575	50,423	(18,848)		19,750
Subawards	G5	108,615	108,615	101,148	7,467		5,958
Other	G6	487,777	94,501	136,431	(41,930)		78,250
Total other direct costs		1,441,423	345,611	369,496	(23,885)		318,398
Total direct costs	H	7,513,403	1,151,982	1,039,408	112,574		1,513,192
Indirect Costs (FY08 provisional 38%)							
	I	2,805,915	396,480	356,406	40,074		572,749
Total direct and indirect costs	J	10,319,318	1,548,462	1,395,815	152,648		2,085,941
ATTACHMENT C							

Attachment D
SUMMARY PROPOSAL BUDGET YEAR TWO

FOR NSF USE ONLY

ORGANIZATION Arctic Research Consortium of the U.S.				PROPOSAL NO.		DURATION (MONTHS)		
PRINCIPAL INVESTIGATOR/PROJECT DIRECTOR Wendy K. Warnick/Helen V. Wiggins				AWARD NO.		Proposed	Granted	
A. SENIOR PERSONNEL: PI/PD, Co-PIs, Faculty and Other Senior Associates List each separately with name and title. (A.7. Show number in brackets)				NSF-Funded Person-months		Funds Requested By Proposer	Funds Granted by NSF (If Different)	
				CAL	ACAD	SUMR		
1. Executive Director – Susan Fox				7			84,339 \$	
2. Director of Programs – Helen V. Wiggins				11			102,100	
3.								
4.								
5.								
6. (0) OTHERS (LIST INDIVIDUALLY ON BUDGET EXPLANATION PAGE)								
7. (2) TOTAL SENIOR PERSONNEL (1-6)							186,439	
B. OTHER PERSONNEL (SHOW NUMBERS IN BRACKETS)								
1. (0) POSTDOCTORAL ASSOCIATES								
2. (9) OTHER PROFESSIONALS (TECHNICIAN, PROGRAMMER, ETC.)				77			348,281	
3. (0) GRADUATE STUDENTS								
4. (2) UNDERGRADUATE STUDENTS							30,215	
5. (2) SECRETARIAL - CLERICAL (IF CHARGED DIRECTLY)							42,406	
6. (0) OTHER								
TOTAL SALARIES AND WAGES (A + B)							607,341	
C. FRINGE BENEFITS (IF CHARGED AS DIRECT COSTS)							230,790	
TOTAL SALARIES, WAGES AND FRINGE BENEFITS (A + B + C)							838,132	
D. EQUIPMENT (LIST ITEM AND DOLLAR AMOUNT FOR EACH ITEM EXCEEDING \$5,000.)								
TOTAL EQUIPMENT								
E. TRAVEL 1. DOMESTIC (INCL. CANADA, MEXICO AND U.S. POSSESSIONS)								67,600
2. FOREIGN								7,800
F. PARTICIPANT SUPPORT								
1. STIPENDS \$ 13,400								
2. TRAVEL 135,300								
3. SUBSISTENCE 132,561								
4. OTHER - 0-								
TOTAL NUMBER OF PARTICIPANTS (84)				TOTAL PARTICIPANT COSTS		281,261		
G. OTHER DIRECT COSTS								
1. MATERIALS AND SUPPLIES								56,290
2. PUBLICATION/DOCUMENTATION/DISSEMINATION								97,950
3. CONSULTANT SERVICES								60,200
4. COMPUTER SERVICES								19,750
5. SUBAWARDS								5,958
6. OTHER								78,250
TOTAL OTHER DIRECT COSTS								318,398
H. TOTAL DIRECT COSTS (A THROUGH G)								1,513,192
I. INDIRECT COSTS (F&A) (SPECIFY RATE AND BASE) 38% on H – G (5)								
TOTAL INDIRECT COSTS (F&A)								572,749
J. TOTAL DIRECT AND INDIRECT COSTS (H + I)								2,085,941
K. RESIDUAL FUNDS (IF FOR FURTHER SUPPORT OF CURRENT PROJECT SEE GPG II.D.7.j.)								152,648
L. AMOUNT OF THIS REQUEST (J) OR (J MINUS K)								\$1,933,293 \$
M. COST SHARING: PROPOSED LEVEL \$				AGREED LEVEL IF DIFFERENT: \$				
PI/PD TYPED NAME AND SIGNATURE* Helen V. Wiggins		DATE 6 April 2009		FOR NSF USE ONLY				
ORG. REP. TYPED NAME & SIGNATURE* Helen V. Wiggins		DATE 6 April 2009		INDIRECT COST RATE VERIFICATION				
				Date Checked	Date of Rate Sheet	Initials-ORG		

1.1 SEARCH Coordination						
Budget by sub-activities						
Totals	A. State of the Arctic	B. Sea Ice Outlook	C. SEARCH-ARCSS Merge	D. Understanding Change Workshop	E. SSC Meetings	F. SEARCH Project Catalog
Wages & Fringe	95144	\$ 25,435.64	\$ 10,125.47	\$ 23,576.89	\$ 14,550.58	\$ 2,278.38
Permanent equipment D	0	0	0	0	0	0
Travel & subsistence-domestic	23400	5200	0	10400	2600	0
Travel & subsistence-foreign	7800	0	0	0	0	0
Travel E	31200	5200	0	10400	2600	0
Stipend	0	0	0	0	0	0
Participant travel	60000	6000	0	42000	6000	0
Participant subsistence	79900	7990	0	55930	7990	0
Participant support costs F	139900	13990	0	97930	13990	0
Office supplies	2000	800	0	1000	100	0
Minor furn & equip	0	0	0	0	0	0
Computer hardware	0	0	0	0	0	0
Computer software	0	0	0	0	0	0
Materials & supplies G1	2000	800	0	1000	100	0
Postage	400	70	0	200	60	0
Shipping	2000	420	0	800	500	0
Duplicating	0	0	0	0	0	0
Printing	2000	450	100	400	600	0
Publication	3000	500	0	2500	0	0
Publ/document/dissemin G2	7400	1440	100	3900	1160	0
Accounting fees	0	0	0	0	0	0
Legal fees	0	0	0	0	0	0
Consulting fees	5000	2000	0	800	200	0
Consultant services G3	5000	2000	0	800	200	0
Computer services G4	4000	1000	500	300	1000	0
Subawards G5	0	0	0	0	0	0
Telephone	3000	100	500	500	500	0
Advertising	0	0	0	0	0	0
Allocated office equip	0	0	0	0	0	0
Subscriptions	0	0	0	0	0	0
Conference fees (attendee)	0	0	0	0	0	0
Office maintenance	0	0	0	0	0	0
Office rent	0	0	0	0	0	0
Storage rent	0	0	0	0	0	0
Staff expenses	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insurance	0	0	0	0	0	0
Temp labor	0	0	0	0	0	0
Miscellaneous	0	0	0	0	0	0
Meeting support	35000	2000	0	28000	5000	0
Meeting fees collected (contra)	0	0	0	0	0	0
Other G6	38000	2100	500	28500	5500	0
Total Other Direct Costs	56400	7340	1100	34500	7960	0
Total Direct costs	322643.55	51966	11225	166407	39101	2278
Indirect costs	122604.55	19747	4266	63235	14858	866
Total direct & indirect costs	\$ 445,248	\$ 71,713	\$ 15,491	\$ 229,642	\$ 53,959	\$ 3,144

1.1 SEARCH Coordination							
Budget by sub-activities							
Totals	G. SEARCH Interagency Meeting	H. AON PI Meeting	I. SSC and Panel Support	J. Coordination with Relevant International Efforts	K. Other Travel Support for SSC Chair/SEARCH rep	L. SEARCH Website	
Wages & Fringe	\$ 856.46	\$ 2,447.68	\$ 5,985.39	\$ 1,229.06	\$ 510.75	\$ 8,147.26	
Permanent equipment D	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Travel & subsistence-domestic	2600	2600	0	0	0	0	
Travel & subsistence-foreign	0	0	0	7800	0	0	
Travel E	2600	2600	0	7800	0	0	
Stipend	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Participant travel	0	0	0	0	6000	0	
Participant subsistence	0	0	0	0	7990	0	
Participant support costs F	0	0	0	0	13990	0	
Office supplies	0	100	0	0	0	0	
Minor furn & equip	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Computer hardware	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Computer software	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Materials & supplies G1	0	100	0	0	0	0	
Postage	0	0	30	40	0	0	
Shipping	0	280	0	0	0	0	
Duplicating	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Printing	100	200	100	50	0	0	
Publication	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Publ/document/dissemin G2	100	480	130	90	0	0	
Accounting fees	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Legal fees	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Consulting fees	0	0	0	0	0	2000	
Consultant services G3	0	0	0	0	0	2000	
Computer services G4	0	0	1000	200	0	0	
Subawards G5	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Telephone	100	200	1000	100	0	0	
Advertising	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Allocated office equip	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Subscriptions	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Conference fees (attendee)	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Office maintenance	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Office rent	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Storage rent	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Staff expenses	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Insurance	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Temp labor	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Miscellaneous	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Meeting support	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Meeting fees collected (contra)	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Other G6	100	200	1000	100	0	0	
Total Other Direct Costs	200	780	2130	390	0	2000	
Total Direct costs	3656	5828	8115	9419	14501	10147	
Indirect costs	1389	2215	3084	3579	5510	3856	
Total direct & indirect costs	\$ 5,046	\$ 8,042	\$ 11,199	\$ 12,998	\$ 20,011	\$ 14,003	

Cell: G35

Comment: Travel for 2 staff

Cell: I35

Comment: Travel for 4 staff

Cell: J35

Comment: 1 staff

Cell: L35

Comment: 1 staff

Cell: M35

Comment: 1 staff

Cell: O36

Comment: Approx. 2 international trips for SSC chair or designee

Cell: G40

Comment: Support for 5

Cell: I40

Comment: Support for 35

Cell: J40

Comment: Support for 5

Cell: P40

Comment: Support for SSC Chair or designee to 5 meetings

Cell: D62

Comment: Wimba software licensing for eMeetings

2.1.1. ARCSS Coordination				
Budget by sub-activities				
Totals	A. Merge ARCSS and SEARCH	B. ARCSS Committee Meetings	C. HARC Subaward	
Wages & Fringe	62,003	24,414	37,589	-
Permanent equipment D	0	0	0	0
Travel & subsistence-domestic	5200	2600	2600	0
Travel & subsistence-foreign	0	0	0	0
Travel E	5200	2600	2600	0
Stipend	12000	6,000	6,000	0
Participant travel	24000	18000	6000	0
Participant subsistence	31964	23973	7991	0
Participant support costs F	67964	47973	19991	0
Office supplies	200	0	200	0
Minor furn & equip	0	0	0	0
Computer hardware	0	0	0	0
Computer software	0	0	0	0
Materials & supplies G1	200	0	200	0
Postage	160	0	160	0
Shipping	0	0	0	0
Duplicating	0	0	0	0
Printing	0	0	0	0
Publication	0	0	0	0
Pub/document/dissemin G2	160	0	160	0
Accounting fees	0	0	0	0
Legal fees	0	0	0	0
Consulting fees	1200	600	600	0
Consultant services G3	1200	600	600	0
Computer services G4	3000	1000	2000	0
Subawards G5	5958	0	0	5958
Telephone	1700	300	1400	0
Advertising	0	0	0	0
Allocated office equip	0	0	0	0
Subscriptions	0	0	0	0
Conference fees (attendee)	0	0	0	0
Office maintenance	0	0	0	0
Office rent	0	0	0	0
Storage rent	0	0	0	0
Staff expenses	0	0	0	0
Insurance	0	0	0	0
Temp labor	0	0	0	0
Miscellaneous	0	0	0	0
Meeting support	10000	5,000	5,000	0
Meeting fees collected (contra)	0	0	0	0
Other G6	11700	5300	6400	0
Total Other Direct Costs	22,218	6,900	9,360	5,958
Total Direct costs	157,387	81,888	69,541	5,959
Indirect costs	57,543	31,117	26,426	0
Total direct & indirect costs	\$214,930	\$ 113,006	\$ 95,967	\$ 5,959

Travel for 1 ARCUS staff

Travel for 1 ARCUS staff

Support for 5

Support for 15 ARCSS participants to Understanding Change workshop

Funds remaining from Year 1 for HARC (no new funds requested)

BUDGET JUSTIFICATION FOR SUBAWARD HARC

The HARC subaward is continued from 2008; no new funds are requested for 2009 - \$5,958 was carried over from 2008. This subaward is to support activities of the HARC Core Office at the University of Alaska Fairbanks through 31 December 2009.

The funds remaining will be used by HARC to complete a Synthesis Report summarizing ten years of HARC research, priorities for research, assessment of state of human dimensions research within arctic science, and a bibliography of HARC research publications. This document also will include a long-term vision/strategic plan to ensure continued and increased proposal pressure and to facilitate community awareness of opportunities for national, international, and interdisciplinary collaborative research and scholarly development in human dimensions research in the arctic. A final report will be produced in 2009 and made available online as a PDF and distributed via the HARC website and relevant mailing lists, with a small printing of the Executive Summary.